

THE UNIVERSITY OF ARIZONA
GRADUATE COLLEGE

As members of the Final Examination Committee, we certify that we have read
the dissertation prepared by Mark Scott Marley

entitled NONRADIAL OSCILLATIONS OF SATURN: IMPLICATIONS FOR RING SYSTEM
STRUCTURE

and recommend that it be accepted as fulfilling the dissertation requirement
for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy.

William B. Hubbard

William B. Hubbard

2/09/90

Date

Jonathan I. Lunine

Jonathan I. Lunine

2/09/90

Date

Richard J. Greenberg

Richard J. Greenberg

2/09/90

Date

Richard L. Shoemaker

Richard L. Shoemaker

2/09/90

Date

Date

Final approval and acceptance of this dissertation is contingent upon the
candidate's submission of the final copy of the dissertation to the Graduate
College.

I hereby certify that I have read this dissertation prepared under my
direction and recommend that it be accepted as fulfilling the dissertation
requirement.

William B. Hubbard

Dissertation Director, William B. Hubbard

2/09/90

Date

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SIGNED: Mark J. Marley

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

“Follow your bliss ... and doors will open where you didn't know they would be.”

— Joseph Campbell

I'm not sure, but it may have been that morning in 1976 when my father and I got up early to watch the first Viking lander image arrive, line by line, in my living room that I discovered my bliss (and that Mars looked a lot like my native Arizona). I have been incredibly fortunate that a long succession of doors subsequently opened. To all the people who helped along the way, I owe enormous gratitude.

In particular I want to thank Dave Stevenson, my undergraduate advisor, for giving me some extraordinary opportunities to explore planetary research at a tender age. My friends from the 'old country' Mark Waggoner, Joe Burfoot, Dave Hawley, Jim Determan, Joe Lee, Paul Gillespie, and Greg 'Hermetian' Bala helped me survive Pasadena and still help keep me sane. In Tucson, my comrades Shelly Pope, Anne Spitz, Ann Sprague, Tom Jones, and Jeff Garland rescued me many times from the tedium of graduate school. To them and all the other graduate students who have helped make my time here so enjoyable, I send my appreciation and best wishes. I especially thank Bob Marcialis for designing most of the `TEX` macros that made producing this document so easy.

I also owe thanks to someone I hardly know, Paul Rosen. His thorough analysis of the C-ring waves provided almost all the data this dissertation tries to explain. Carolyn Porco, who initially filed the seismology concept under 'Numerology', has been a valued supporter and collaborator. Her careful reading of Chapter 3 resulted in numerous improvements.

My advisor, Bill Hubbard, deserves special thanks. His guidance, flexibility, and support opened many doors during my tenure here. I especially thank him for his generosity with both his time and his resources. The freedom he has given me to pursue this project as I saw fit is most appreciated. I also thank the other members of my committee, Rick Greenberg, Jonathan Lunine, and Richard Shoemaker for constructive criticism and good ideas. Support for this project was primarily provided by the NASA Graduate Student Researchers Program, grant NGT-50049.

When I arrived in Tucson, it occurred to me that I might meet my future wife here. I never guessed she would be a Jersey girl. Ginny Gulick's help has been vital during every stage of the production of this document. Without her, I would not be writing this now. She has brought me more joy than I ever thought possible.

Finally, I thank the people who have been opening doors for me for almost 28 years: my parents. Their constant support and encouragement are the real reason I could follow my bliss. So to Denzil and Louise Marley, I dedicate this dissertation.

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ABSTRACT

Numerous wave and gap features observed in Voyager data of Saturn's rings are produced by resonances between the orbital frequencies of known external satellites and ring particle orbits. This thesis investigates the possibility that other, currently unassociated, ring features are generated by perturbations on ring particle orbits produced by non-axisymmetric gravitational fields resulting from acoustic oscillation modes of the planet. The frequencies of Saturnian low degree ($l \leq 8$) fundamental (or f) mode oscillations are calculated for a variety of Saturn interior models which span the range of uncertainty of the interior structure of the planet. Corrections for rotation, oblateness, and possible differential rotation have been applied. Only the low degree f-modes are found to have frequencies and likely wave amplitudes in the range necessary to produce gap or wave features in the rings. The calculated positions of outer Lindblad resonances (OLR) for the degree $l = 2, 3, 4,$ and 5 sectoral f-modes of a single Saturn model lie near four previously unassociated C-ring features. These features are the Maxwell gap and three waves identified as being forced at either OLR or inner vertical resonances. The outer vertical resonance (OVR) of the $l = 5, m = 4$ mode also overlaps the location of a wave which may be forced at either an OVR or an inner Lindblad resonance. Four other similar wave features, however, cannot be explained by oscillation mode resonances. This failure to account for all of the comparable unassociated C-ring waves is the principal inadequacy of the hypothesis. Other observed properties of the wave features, however, including their azimuthal wavenumbers m and the variation of amplitude with proposed oscillation mode degree are consistent with the proposed forcing. Planetary oscillation amplitudes of ~ 1 m are required for gap opening; wave amplitudes of ~ 10 cm are required for density wave production. The

C-ring thus serves as a very sensitive f-mode detector. Observations by the Cassini spacecraft should unequivocally determine if the C-ring features are produced by planetary oscillation modes. If these observations confirm the association, significant new constraints could be placed on Saturnian energy transport, differential rotation, and core size.

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This introduction presents a general background to the major topics covered in this thesis. The importance and methods of studying the interior properties of the Jovian planets are presented, followed by a brief overview of Saturn's rings. Finally there is a discussion relating the two, seemingly disparate, topics and a summary of the contents of the dissertation.

1.1 Saturn Interior Models

Unlike their cloud tops, which may be studied in a variety of ways, the structure of the deep interiors of Jupiter, Saturn, Uranus, and Neptune (the Jovian planets) may only be inferred. Constraints on the interior structures of these bodies have traditionally come from a handful of observational areas: the planets' gravitational moments, shapes and rotation rates, magnetic fields, atmospheric abundances of important constituents, and equations of state of hydrogen, helium, and heavier elements at high pressure. Table 1.1 lists some of the physical parameters upon which Saturnian interior models are based (*e.g.* Hubbard and Horedt 1983; Hubbard and Marley 1989).

The structures of the deep interiors of the Jovian planets are of interest for a variety of reasons. The inferred similarity of the core masses of the Jovian planets is one of the principal arguments in favor of the core instability process (Pollack 1985), a widely accepted theory of giant planet formation. Models of the solar nebula are often driven to provide the environment presumed necessary to satisfy the theoretical requirements for the formation of the Jovian planets, especially Jupiter.

Table 1.1

Primary Constraints on Saturnian Interior Structure

a (km)	GM_S ($\text{km}^3 \text{s}^{-2}$)	$\Omega_0 \times 10^8$ (s^{-1})	$J_2 \times 10^6$	$J_4 \times 10^6$	$J_6 \times 10^6$
$60,268 \pm 4$	$97,931,200 \pm 100$	$16,378 \pm 4$	$16,331 \pm 18$	-914 ± 61	108 ± 50

(a from Lindal *et al.* 1985; gravity data from Nicholson and Porco 1988, normalized to a ; magnetospheric rotation rate from Kaiser *et al.* 1984)

These same models must then also account for the other observed properties of the solar system. In a very real sense, understanding the origin and evolution of the solar system depends upon understanding the interior structure of the Jovian planets. The molecular and metallic hydrogen envelopes of Jupiter and Saturn provide a testing ground for the equation of state of dense hydrogen/helium mixtures (*e.g.* Hubbard and Marley 1987). Furthermore the thermal evolution of these planets subsequent to their formation depends on their interior structure. For example, slight interior composition gradients, detectable through interior modelling, can have a very large impact on the ability of the planets to transport energy through convection (Stevenson 1982a).

Although the overall interior structures of these planets are fairly well constrained, several aspects are still relatively uncertain. Many uncertainties revolve around the central cores, which are presumed to be composed of rock and ices. It is not known, for example, if the cores consist of a single rocky layer, with the planets' allotment of ices mixed into their upper atmospheres, or if there are two core layers, an inner rocky one and an outer icy one. Another uncertainty is whether the central core is distinct and surrounded by an essentially homogeneous, adiabatic envelope or if the core/envelope boundary is indistinct with an envelope stratified into regions of varying compositions (Stevenson 1985). The uncertainties in the

gravitational harmonics, listed in Table 1.1, while small, still produce relatively large uncertainties in interior structure. The error bar on the gravitational component J_4 , for example, translates directly into a core mass uncertainty of $\sim 60\%$ (Hubbard and Marley 1989). All core related uncertainties combine to yield a core mass uncertain within a factor of two (Hubbard and Marley 1989). Yet it is the size and structure of the core that may yield the most pertinent information regarding cosmogonic scenarios.

Since all relevant observational data are used to construct consistent Jovian planet interior models, there has been no means to test independently the accuracy and veracity of these models, except to compare results among researchers using the same data. Thus any new means of studying the deep interiors of these planets would be useful for testing the current stable of models. One possibility comes from the field of solar research. Two decades or so ago the study of the solar interior similarly required a new window into the depths of the sun. Such an opening came in the form of helioseismology. Helioseismology, the study of the sun's natural acoustic oscillations, has successfully probed the solar interior. The well-known 5-minute solar oscillations, for example, result from the superposition of numerous acoustic oscillation modes. These oscillations have periods of ~ 5 minutes, contain information about the solar interior, and are easily detectable in the doppler shift of spectral lines in the solar atmosphere (Christensen-Dalsgaard *et al.* 1985). Unfortunately, similar oscillations on Jupiter or Saturn are very difficult to detect directly and no attempt has yet been successful (Deming *et al.* 1989). Because of the small expected mode amplitudes, Deming *et al.* searched not for doppler shifted absorption lines, but rather for the appearance of oscillation induced atmospheric effects in the infrared. They placed an upper limit on total mode velocities of about

1 m s^{-1} for modes with periods near 10 minutes. The much longer period f-mode oscillations, the subject of this work, are almost certainly not detectable by this means (Mosser 1990).

The frequencies of the natural oscillations of a star or Jovian planet depend on the interior structure of the body. In the same way that the tone emitted by an organ pipe can indicate the size and shape of the pipe, the frequencies at which a planet resonates may reveal details of its interior structure. Mosser *et al.* (1988), for example, have demonstrated that the frequencies of certain acoustic oscillations of Jupiter may contain information on Jupiter's core size. There has not been, however, any systematic attempt to determine how sensitive Jovian planet oscillations are to variations in interior models and other associated assumptions. This thesis begins to fill that void by systematically studying those aspects which have the greatest impact on Saturnian f-mode oscillations. This particular planet and set of oscillation modes are chosen since a new oscillation detection technique is most sensitive to these modes and may only be used at Saturn.

1.2 Exploration and Geography of Saturn's Rings

Since they were first observed by Galileo in 1610, the rings of Saturn both have puzzled and fascinated observers. In Earth based telescopes, the rings appear to be divided into 3 broad, relatively homogeneous, sections with several gaps and divisions. Until recently very little else was known about the radial structure of the rings. This situation changed dramatically when the Voyager spacecraft encountered Saturn. The Voyagers probed the rings with a variety of instruments and found them to be incredibly complex and striking. Perhaps the most surprising discovery by the spacecraft was that the rings were not bland and homogeneous,

Table 1.2
Ring Nomenclature and Dimensions†

Ring Region	Boundary (km)	Orbital Frequency Ω (10^{-4} s^{-1})
----- D	66,970	3.554
----- C	74,510	3.028
----- B	92,000	2.207
----- Cassini Division	117,580	1.528
----- A	122,170	1.442
-----	136,780	1.218

†Table excerpted from Cuzzi *et al.* (1984).

but rather consisted of many small, complex structures. Literally thousands of ringlets, bands, waves, and gaps were seen in the data. Table 1.2 summarizes the terminology applied to the largest ring structures.

Occultation measurements provided one of the most effective ways of gathering information about the rings. In these experiments the attenuation of an electromagnetic signal traversing the rings is measured. From the attenuation a radial profile of the amount of ring material *vs.* radius is found. For example a photopolarimeter on the spacecraft measured the variation of starlight as a star appeared to pass behind the rings due to the motion of the spacecraft. Even more useful for studying relatively thin regions of the rings were the radio science occultations. In these experiments, the radio signal from the spacecraft to the Earth was caused to pass through the rings. From the amplitude and phase information received on

Figure 1.1. RSS occultation of Ring C. Radio science opacity τ_{RSS} and hence quantity of material at a given radius increases upwards. Analysis of individual features takes place at much higher resolution.

the ground, very accurate maps of the ring structure could be made. The most accurate and complete such map is that of Rosen (1989). Figure 1.1 shows part of a radio occultation profile of Saturn's C-ring.

With the orders-of-magnitude increase in information on the structure of the rings came similar increases in the number of questions about them. It was soon determined, however, that some of the gaps, waves, and ringlets, seen in the data were produced by gravitational resonances with the many satellites of Saturn. The

theory is presented in Chapter 3, but an analogy illustrates the concept. When pushing a child on a swing it is important to always push in phase with the pendulum swing of the child. A series of regular, gentle pushes can send the child soaring. A satellite orbiting Saturn also pushes and pulls gravitationally on the many small ring particles that make up the rings. If the gravitational perturbations are in phase with natural periodicities of the ring particles, large amplitude excursions in the orbits of the particles can be excited. Since these particles are part of a disk, collisions and angular momentum transport processes are also important. Thus the result of a resonance is a wave superimposed on the equilibrium structure of the disk. Waves in the disk can take the form of variations in the areal number density (density waves) or actual warpings of the ring plane (bending waves). Both varieties of ripples can be seen in ring images and occultation data. If the forcing is even stronger, a gap in the rings, where the ring particles have been cleared away, may appear. Such resonance theory has been very successful in explaining a great many of the gaps and waves seen in the rings. Many other similar appearing features, however, remain unexplained. Some of these features might be produced by satellites unseen by the Voyager spacecraft. Other waves seem to require satellites so large that they should already have been detected (Rosen 1989). In the next section I introduce an alternative to satellites as a driver of such structures.

1.3 Making Waves

In order to explain some of these remaining features in the rings, new and imaginative ideas have been proposed. Franklin *et al.* (1982) suggested that permanent ‘lumps’ inside Saturn, carried around by the rotation of the planet, might create gravitational perturbations similar to those caused by an external satellite. The

interior of Saturn, however, is believed to be fluid, making the existence of Saturnian mountains unlikely. Also the location of the resonances in the rings would be fixed by the rotation period. Holberg *et al.* (1982) searched the ring data for the signature of such lumps and came up empty handed. Permanent mountains inside the planet do not explain any ring feature. But if permanent lumps do not exist, what about transitory ones? Waves propagating through the planet might disturb the equilibrium density profile sufficiently to perturb orbits of ring particles.

Coriolis-dominated “inertial modes” of Saturn were suggested by Stevenson (1982b) as a source of perturbations to the external gravitational field of the planet. Inertial oscillations are oscillatory motions of a rotating fluid that are not produced by free surfaces, compressibility, or density stratification (Aldridge and Toomre 1969). These modes would produce density perturbations in the planet which in turn would affect the external gravitational field. Since the modes propagate around the planet, the location of their resonances in the rings would not be fixed by the rotation period. The inertial mode frequencies are capable of producing resonances in the rings (Stevenson 1982b). Unfortunately the exact periods of these modes are very difficult to calculate and no one has yet done so, rendering this hypothesis essentially untestable.

Also in 1982, Hubbard (personal communication) proposed that the acoustic modes of Saturn might provide the travelling density lumps necessary to perturb the gravitational field. These modes are basically resonant acoustic waves propagating inside Saturn and thus differ substantially from the inertial modes. The predicted acoustic oscillation frequencies (Vorontsov *et al.* 1976) were indeed in the correct range to produce resonances in the rings. How sensitive these frequencies were to interior conditions was unknown. Marley, Hubbard and Porco (1987) expanded on

this idea and specifically proposed that single resonances between acoustic oscillations and ring particle orbits could produce gaps and waves in Saturn's C-ring. Lin *et al.* (1987) independently invoked acoustic modes in suggesting that closely spaced pairs of resonances between acoustic oscillation modes and ring particle orbits could confine narrow rings, an especially pressing problem at Uranus.

Thus this confluence of problems, the need for more information about the interior of all Jovian planets, including Saturn, and the need to explain features in Saturn's rings, gave rise to planetary ring seismology. Perhaps by finding the signature of planetary oscillations in the rings, the exact oscillation frequency of a given oscillation mode of the planet could be determined. From a set of such oscillation frequencies, a great deal about the interior structure of the planet might be revealed and several unexplained ring features accounted for.

Before a search for planet-produced ring features can begin, however, many questions need to be answered. First, what are the oscillation frequencies for a variety of Saturn models? How sensitive are these frequencies to changes in the interior structure? What other uncertainties are important, such as rotation or the presence of internal composition gradients? How great are the density perturbations produced in the interior of the planet? Are they large enough to perturb the gravitational field to the extent necessary to create gaps and waves in the rings? How are these oscillations excited? Can they be excited to sufficient amplitudes by known mechanisms? While a beginning had been made towards addressing some of the oscillation oriented questions, chiefly by Vorontsov and colleagues (Vorontsov and Zharkov 1981; Vorontsov 1981; Vorontsov 1984a; Vorontsov 1984b), only a single Saturn model was studied and there were still many unanswered questions.

This dissertation attempts to answer these queries. In short, “Are Saturn’s rings a seismograph? If so, what does the seismograph tell us?”.

Chapter 2 explains the oscillatory behavior of Saturn more fully and provides the mathematical underpinnings of the acoustic oscillations of the planet. Chapter 3 examines the rings and develops the theory to relate the oscillations to gaps and waves which might be observed in the rings. Also a list of unexplained ring features which might be accounted for by planetary oscillation modes is presented. Chapter 4 discusses the results of oscillation frequency calculations for a great variety of Saturn interior models and examines the sensitivity of the results to various assumptions. Finally Chapter 5 uses these frequencies to determine where in the rings features might be seen and compares these predictions with the observations. Chapter 6 provides an overview and summary of all the results.

CHAPTER 2

JOVIAN PLANET OSCILLATORY BEHAVIOR

This Chapter presents the theoretical background to oscillations of Jovian planets. A discussion of the types of oscillation modes and their mathematical underpinnings is followed by sections considering the effect of planetary rotation on the oscillations, and the overall accuracy of the theory. In the final section, oscillation excitation is discussed.

2.1 Description of the Oscillation Modes

There are a variety of oscillation modes which can be supported on a rotating fluid body like Jupiter or Saturn. These modes are characterized by the principal restoring force acting on the fluid. Pressure can act as a restoring force in purely radial pulsations, where the oscillating fluid has no azimuthal component of displacement. Both pressure and gravity (acting through buoyancy) can provide restoring forces for nonradial oscillations, which do have an azimuthal component of displacement. Which particular force is more important depends on the frequency and wavelength of the perturbation. A third type of oscillation, the inertial oscillation modes, arise from the action of the coriolis force in a rotating fluid. This thesis considers the nonradial oscillation modes of Saturn.

The nonradial oscillation modes of a fluid planet or star are further divided into classes by the principal restoring force. Buoyancy driven internal gravity waves propagate at low frequency; pressure driven acoustic waves propagate at high frequency. If these waves are trapped in a resonant cavity inside the planet, some will

Figure 2.1. Illustration of surface spherical harmonics for degree $l = 4$. Figure from Unno *et al.* (1979).

constructively interfere with themselves. The pattern produced by their constructive interference is described as an oscillation mode of the planet. Only waves of certain frequencies will resonate inside any given cavity. Thus an oscillation mode is characterized by the type of waves in resonance, the interference pattern produced by these waves, and the frequency of oscillation. The g-modes are standing internal gravity waves and generally oscillate at low frequency. The p-modes are standing acoustic waves and generally oscillate at high frequency. The f-modes are of intermediate frequency and can be regarded as the fundamental mode of either the p- or g-modes. For an intuitive discussion of the behavior of these waves and modes see the review by Leibacher and Stein (1981).

Regardless of the type of oscillation, each produces perturbations to the equilibrium density ρ , pressure p , and gravitational potential Φ of the planet. Since these are waves on a spherical body and since the governing differential equations are separable, these perturbations are all proportional to the surface spherical harmonics $Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi)$. An example is the Eulerian perturbation to the pressure at a given position in the planet,

$$p'(r, \theta, \varphi) = p'(r)Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi)e^{-i\sigma t}. \quad (2.1)$$

Throughout this thesis, r is the radius, θ is the colatitude, φ is the azimuth angle, and σ is the oscillation frequency. Note that I follow the usual practice of referring to both the radial part of the perturbation and the full expression with the same symbol. The surface spherical harmonics may be normalized in a variety of ways; the following is the explicit version used in this thesis:

$$Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) = (-1)^{(m+|m|)/2} \left[\frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \frac{(l-|m|)!}{(l+|m|)!} \right]^{1/2} P_l^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\varphi}. \quad (2.2)$$

Finally the expression for the displacement vector $\vec{\xi}$, is given by

$$\vec{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \left[\xi_r(r), \xi_h(r) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta}, \xi_h(r) \frac{\partial}{\sin \theta \partial \varphi} \right] Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) e^{-i\sigma t}. \quad (2.3)$$

Note that vector quantities are boldface, unless they are greek characters in which case a vector symbol is used. A given oscillation mode is thus described by the three integers l , m , and n . On a spherical surface the oscillation degree l measures the number of border lines between regions of positive and negative perturbation. The oscillation order m ($= -l, -l+1, \dots, 0, \dots, l-1, l$) counts the number of azimuthal border lines. Figure 2.1 illustrates the surface spherical harmonics for the case $l = 4$. The radial order n counts the number of radial nodes in the radial

Figure 2.2. Illustration of travelling wave nature of $l = |m| = 2$ non-radial oscillation mode. The pattern travels about the polar axis in the same or opposite direction as the rotation depending on the sign of m . Figure from Unno *et al.* (1979).

displacement eigenfunction. The notation conventions used here are derived from Unno *et al.* (1979). The objective of the eigenvalue calculation is to determine $\xi_r(r)$, $\xi_h(r)$, $p'(r)$, $\Phi'(r)$, and $\rho'(r)$.

For $m \neq 0$ the pattern propagates in the azimuthal direction with a phase velocity

$$v_p = \frac{\sigma}{m} \quad (2.4)$$

in the rest frame of the planet. Positive m modes propagate around the polar axis in the direction of rotation. For reasons explained in Chapter 3, in connection with ring resonances I will almost always be considering the special case $m = l$. Figure 2.2 illustrates such a travelling wave.

2.2 Nonradial Oscillation Eigenvalue Problem

For adiabatic, nonradial oscillations the governing differential equations are as follows (Unno *et al.* 1979; eqs. 13.1 – 13.3):

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} (r^2 \xi_r) - \frac{g}{c^2} \xi_r + \left(1 - \frac{L_l^2}{\sigma^2}\right) \frac{p'}{\rho c^2} = \frac{l(l+1)}{\sigma^2 r^2} \Phi', \quad (2.5)$$

$$\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{dp'}{dr} + \frac{g}{\rho c^2} p' + (N^2 - \sigma^2) \xi_r = -\frac{d\Phi'}{dr}, \quad (2.6)$$

and

$$\frac{1}{r^2} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^2 \frac{d\Phi'}{dr} \right) - \frac{l(l+1)}{r^2} \Phi' = 4\pi G \rho \left(\frac{p'}{\rho c^2} + \frac{N^2}{g} \xi_r \right). \quad (2.7)$$

Where ξ_r is the radial part of the displacement in the radial direction, $c = (\Gamma p_0 / \rho_0)^{1/2}$ is the sound speed, and the two frequencies are the Lamb frequency L_l ,

$$L_l^2 = \frac{l(l+1)c^2}{r^2} \quad (2.8)$$

and the Brunt–Väisälä frequency N ,

$$N^2 = g \left(\frac{1}{\Gamma} \frac{d \ln p_0}{dr} - \frac{d \ln \rho_0}{dr} \right). \quad (2.9)$$

The adiabatic exponent $\Gamma = (d \ln p_0 / d \ln \rho_0)_{\text{ad}}$, G is the gravitation constant, g is the gravitational acceleration at r , and r is the radius. Primed variables refer to the Eulerian perturbation at a given position; zero subscripts refer to the unperturbed value.

Equations 2.5 – 2.7 are the full fourth-order set of differential equations. There are four corresponding boundary conditions (Unno *et al.* 1979; eqs. 13.7–13.10).

At $r = 0$,

$$\frac{d\Phi'}{dr} - \frac{l\Phi'}{r} = 0 \quad (2.10)$$

and

$$\xi_r - \frac{l}{\sigma^2 r} \left(\frac{p'}{\rho} + \Phi' \right) = 0. \quad (2.11)$$

At $r = R$, where R is the radius of the planet,

$$\frac{d\Phi'}{dr} + \frac{(l+1)}{r} \Phi' = 0 \quad (2.12)$$

and

$$\delta p = 0. \quad (2.13)$$

Here δ is the Lagrangian perturbation for a given fluid element. Equation 2.13 has various limiting forms, depending on the physical conditions at $r = R$. For the case in which the density and pressure vanish at the surface, (2.13) can be written (Unno *et al.* 1979; eq. 17.49),

$$\xi_r - \frac{p'}{g\rho} = 0, \quad (2.14)$$

which is equivalent to

$$\frac{\delta p}{p} = 0. \quad (2.15)$$

This condition is valid whenever

$$-\frac{d \ln p}{d \ln r} = \frac{r}{H} \gg 1 \quad (2.16)$$

at $r = R$. Since the pressure scale height H at 1 bar in Saturn's atmosphere is about 40 km this condition for a free boundary is appropriate. The differential equations, boundary conditions, and a normalization condition at $r = R$, $\xi_r/r = 1$, comprise the eigenvalue problem.

The first investigation of oscillations of Jupiter and Saturn was by Vorontsov *et al.* (1976). In addition to the above formulation, they considered boundary conditions applied at interior jumps of the planet's material parameters, such as

produced by a first order phase transitions and the core/envelope boundary. In doing so they found a class of gravity waves trapped at such interfaces. The periods of these modes, the low degree f- and p-mode oscillation periods, and eigenfunctions are presented in their paper. They also provide numerical values for the first order rotation corrections to the eigenfrequencies. These correction values are incorrect and were modified in subsequent papers.

In two later papers, Vorontsov (1984a, 1984b) further considered the impact of phase boundaries on the calculation of the zeroth order eigenfrequencies. In the first paper (1984a) Vorontsov more carefully investigated the interior boundary conditions that should be applied at a phase transition. He found that the 1976 paper incorrectly treated the phase transition boundary and that the periods of certain modes should be modified by up to several percent. Also the phase boundary layer modes disappear when using the new boundary treatment. The fundamental modes, however, were found to be insensitive to the detailed treatment of the boundary condition, and the greatest error (in the $l = 2$ f-mode) was 0.1%. Vorontsov (1984b) also considered a less distinct phase boundary, such as one blurred by convection. A similar situation would be produced by a non first order phase transition. In such cases no interior boundary conditions are needed and numerical integration can proceed directly across the transition zone. In the final paper, Vorontsov developed a perturbation method to calculate the frequency corrections due to the change in the internal boundary condition.

Jovian p-mode oscillation frequencies have also been calculated by Bercovici and Schubert (1987), Mosser *et al.* (1988), and Deming *et al.* (1989). These calculations were all for intermediate to high degree overtones ($n \gtrsim 5$) and thus could use various asymptotic approximations to solve for the eigenfrequencies. Since f-modes

are required to produce ring perturbations, these results are not directly applicable to this work. The Jovian results of Mosser *et al.* (1988), however, were used to verify the oscillation eigenfrequencies calculation procedure.

2.3 Rotation Corrections

The eigenvalue problem as presented above is appropriate only for non-rotating objects. In the case of a rotating Jovian planet, the single most important new consideration is the Coriolis force: in the frame of the planet modes travelling in the direction of rotation have longer periods while modes travelling in the opposite direction have shorter periods. Rather than carry out a whole new eigenfrequency calculation, the effects of rotation are typically modelled by a perturbation method. The first order correction for the Coriolis force is well known (Unno *et al.* 1979; eq. 18.32) and is proportional to the order m and the rotational frequency Ω_P . Jupiter and Saturn, however, rotate quite rapidly. Rapid rotation implies that forces arising in Ω_P^2 , such as the centrifugal force, may also play an important role in the oscillations. Also the figures of both Jupiter and Saturn are significantly perturbed by rotation and the rotation rates may vary with depth in the planet (Zharkov and Trubitsyn 1978). Vorontsov and Zharkov addressed these and other issues in two papers (Vorontsov and Zharkov 1981; Vorontsov 1981) and found that the higher order effects could also be accounted for in the framework of perturbation theory.

Vorontsov and Zharkov (1981) developed the theory in the case of rigid body rotation. They also accounted for interaction of modes, a process which may produce eigenmodes of mixed character. Perturbation theory fails when such mode interaction is too great. The modes which experience the greatest influence of rotation

are the f-modes, hence they would be most prone to experience mode interaction. The calculations, however, demonstrated that f-mode interaction was slight. The disagreement between frequency calculations which considered mode interaction and those which neglected it never exceeded 1%. In addition the disagreement was greatest for large l modes. For the mode $l = m = 6$, the contribution of mode interaction to the eigenfrequency is 1%; for lower l the effect is significantly less. In the subsequent papers Vorontsov neglects mode interaction since accounting for it considerably complicates the perturbation theory. I make the same approximation.

In this thesis I use the perturbation approach of Vorontsov (1981) to calculate the rotation corrections. This method accurately treats all rotation effects through second order, including Coriolis forces, centrifugal forces, and ellipticity of the planet's figure as well as allowing for differential rotation. The oscillation frequency $\tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n}$ found for the non-rotating case (henceforth the tilde applies to quantities found in the case of no rotation) is modified through a series expansion. The expression for the oscillation frequency $\sigma_{l,m,n}$ observed from an inertial frame is then

$$\sigma_{l,m,n} = \tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n}(1 + \sigma_{l,m,n,1}\lambda + \sigma_{l,m,n,2}\lambda^2 + \dots), \quad (2.17)$$

where the small parameter

$$\lambda = \frac{\Omega_0}{\tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n}} \quad (2.18)$$

and the rotational frequency is expanded in spherical harmonics,

$$\Omega_P = \Omega_P(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \Omega_d(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \sum_i^k \Omega_{di}(r) Y_{i,0}(\theta, \varphi). \quad (2.19)$$

The oscillation eigenfunctions may be similarly perturbed. Note that in the absence of rotation the frequencies are degenerate with respect to the oscillation degree m .

To quantify the effects of rotation, the σ parameters in (2.17) must be calculated. In the absence of differential rotation, σ_1 reduces to the well documented Coriolis correction alluded to earlier (Unno *et al.* 1979). This correction breaks the degeneracy in m . Including differential rotation does not complicate the problem greatly, and the expression is straightforward (Vorontsov 1981; eq. 49). The expression, which is reproduced fully in Appendix I as Eq. A1.15, involves an integral over radius of the radial and horizontal fluid displacement eigenfunctions, the unperturbed density, and various angular integrals. Calculation of σ_2 , however, is far more complex. The expression for σ_2 , derived from Vorontsov's (1981) equation (39), is

$$2\sigma_{l,m,n,2} - \sigma_{l,m,n,1}^2 = K_{1t} + K_{1s} + K_2 + K_3. \quad (2.20)$$

Each of the terms on the right hand side of the equation accounts for different consequences of rotation. The two K_1 terms represent torsional and spheroidal type corrections. K_2 accounts for inertial forces and is proportional to m . Finally K_3 reflects the influence of centrifugal forces and ellipticity of figure. The expressions for all of these terms are quite complex and are also relegated to Appendix I. Terms K_{1t} , K_{1s} , and K_2 are given as equations A1.18 – A1.20. K_3 is even more involved than the other terms and is itself comprised of the sum of 6 terms derived in Vorontsov and Zharkov (1981) and given here as equations A1.23 – A1.28. The salient properties of these expressions are discussed below.

The first three terms of equation (2.20), like the expression for σ_1 , involve integrals over the product of unperturbed density and various permutations of the oscillation eigenfunctions. Components of the differential rotation expression Ω_{di} and angular integrals also appear. The expressions also involve sums over the differential rotation index i and oscillation degree l . Since in practice the degree of

the expansion of differential rotation (k in eq. 2.19) does not exceed 2, these sums consist of only several terms, each an integral. Beyond calculating the correct sums and products for each individual term in each integral, no new model calculations are required. This is not the case for the final term K_3 .

Since term K_3 accounts for ellipticity of figure and centrifugal forces, the detailed distribution of matter inside the planet is of great importance. Quantities involved in this calculation include not only those mentioned above, but also various derivatives of numerous different parameters. These includes derivatives of the compression modulus (or more exactly, the adiabatic modulus of incompressibility)

$$K_s = \Gamma p \tag{2.21}$$

and the gravitational potential Φ , as well as integrals over products of these terms and other functions of radius including the ellipticity of level surfaces $\epsilon(r)$. There are also terms which may account for discrete jumps in material parameters, as might occur at a first order phase transition or the core/envelope boundary. Due to the nature of the perturbation method, I must stress that the quantities ρ , p , K_s and Φ must be calculated for a *non-rotating* planet. The perturbation method then adjusts these terms for rotation and uses the adjusted terms to correct the eigenfrequencies for rotation. The important quantity in this procedure is then $\epsilon(r)$ which is provided by interior models for rotating planets (*e.g.* Hubbard and Marley 1989). Thus, while tedious to compute, the necessary quantities are derivable from interior models and the oscillation eigenfunctions. This process is discussed in detail in Sections 4.2 and 4.4.

2.4 Accuracy of the Theory

At this point it is worthwhile to step back and consider how accurately the above theories actually model the physical processes leading to oscillations and oscillation modification by rotation. There are two principle sources of uncertainty: model approximations and model appropriateness. The first are recognized in the implementation of the theory, the second are not.

The greatest uncertainty in the theory for the eigenfrequencies of the nonrotating planet arises from the interior boundary conditions. The oscillation eigenmodes are likely to be affected to some extent by the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition and by the transition to a rock or ice core. It is not known, however, whether these transitions are sharp or gradual ones or even exactly where in the planet they are located. Introducing a detailed boundary treatment for at a location where it is not appropriate could introduce a larger error than ignoring the boundary altogether. Fortunately, the low degree f-modes are relatively insensitive to the treatment of these boundaries, with variations in the boundary conditions introducing uncertainties of $\lesssim 0.1\%$ (Section 2.2). Also as discussed in Section 2.2 the correct treatment at a gradual interior boundary is to continue the numerical integration directly across it. For these reasons, I will assume that both the phase and core/envelope boundaries are continuous, thereby avoiding the interior boundary conditions altogether. Neglect of these boundaries, then, should introduce a theoretical error no larger than $\sim 0.2\%$. Numerical experiments confirmed this result.

When considering rotation, however, the theory becomes less certain. Because mode mixing is not considered, errors ranging from $\sim 1\%$ for $l = 6$ to $\sim 0\%$ for $l = 2$ f-modes are introduced (Vorontsov and Zharkov 1981). Of equal concern is

the fact that the perturbation theory only considers terms through second order in Ω_p . Further figure corrections are not introduced until fourth order and no new rotating-frame forces arise in Ω_p^3 . Continuing expansion of the lower order corrections, however, does produce a non-zero σ_3 . Assuming σ_3 , like σ_1 and σ_2 , is of order unity, the magnitude of the third order correction can be estimated. For $l = 2$ neglect of the third order term introduces an error of $\sim 1\%$ while for $l = 6$ the error is $\sim 0.2\%$. Thus the third order error complements the mode mixing error and when combined with the zero order frequency error, an overall uncertainty in the f-mode frequency for each degree l in this range of $\sim 1\%$ is derived.

Beyond the shortcomings of the perturbation method is the question of the applicability of the theory to Jovian and Saturnian oscillations. The differential equations presented in Section 2.1 assume linear, adiabatic oscillations. The first assumption is almost certainly valid since the required amplitudes to produce ring features, as will be discussed in Section 5.4, are only 10 cm to 1 m. These dimensions are orders of magnitude smaller than any other relevant length scale. Also for Jovian planets as a whole the adiabatic approximation is an excellent one. Thermal cooling times for Jupiter and Saturn are about the age of the solar system (Hubbard 1984) while the dynamical times under consideration are just hundreds of minutes. However in regions where the modes are reflected or excited, the time scales must be considered locally (Unno *et al.* 1979). In those regions the degree of adiabaticity is measured by c/v compared with unity (Unno *et al.* 1979), where v is the convective speed. The atmospheric convective velocities for both Jupiter and Saturn are small. Deming *et al.* (1989) has estimated $v \sim 10 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ and $c \sim 10^5 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for p-mode excitation regions in Jupiter, implying a very high degree of adiabaticity. The assumptions of linear and adiabatic oscillations are thus well justified.

It remains, then, to assign a formal uncertainty to the oscillation frequencies computed using this theory. Section 4.1 will consider the uncertainties inherent in the oscillation computation method and Section 4.3 examines how the range of frequencies depends on uncertainties in the interior models. These other uncertainties must all ultimately be compared with the fundamental theoretical errors. Given the above discussion, an error bar equal to 1% of the oscillation frequency seems an appropriate estimate of the theoretical uncertainty.

2.5 Oscillation Excitation

The mechanisms of non-radial oscillation excitation, even on the well studied sun, are still not perfectly understood. This lack of an adequate theory combined with the general uncertainty regarding the deep interiors of Jupiter and Saturn allows only crude order-of-magnitude estimates of expected oscillation amplitudes to be made. In this section I explore the possible oscillation excitation mechanisms and estimate the resulting oscillation amplitudes.

The total energy E contained in an oscillation mode (Unno *et al.* 1979) is given by

$$E = \frac{\sigma^2}{2} \int_0^M |\vec{\xi}|^2 dM_r. \quad (2.22)$$

The integral is taken over the mass distribution of the planet. Using a typical eigenfunction calculated in Chapter 4 and assuming the $l = 2$ f-mode of Saturn is excited to an amplitude at the surface of 1 m, then $E_{2f} \sim 5 \times 10^{26}$ ergs. As the oscillation degree l is increased, the depth to which the mode penetrates into the planet is decreased. Although the oscillation frequency rises with l , higher degree f-modes with the same surface amplitude are characterized by progressively lower

total energy. The total planetary oscillation energy is the sum over all excited modes.

Stellar oscillations are believed to be excited by several different mechanisms. Coupling between temperature and density dependent nuclear energy generation rates and oscillation induced perturbations, known as the ϵ -mechanism, would of course not be relevant to Jovian planets. A coupling between temperature dependent radiative opacities and oscillations is also believed to be an important mechanism for stellar oscillation excitation. This κ -mechanism, however, is not applicable to Jovian planets since the radiative opacity of the deep interior is so large that no significant heat is transported via radiation (Hubbard and Stevenson 1984). A detailed analysis is further precluded since the radiative opacity and derivatives with thermodynamic parameters for dense molecular hydrogen are not well known. Yet another possible excitation mechanism is growth of oscillations through radiative and convective diffusion of thermal energy, known as the Cowling or δ mechanism (Unno *et al.* 1979). Since radiative transport is unimportant, the radiative Cowling mechanism is probably also of little consequence. The impact of this mechanism is also smaller than the convective Cowling mechanism (Unno *et al.* 1979). Order of magnitude calculations from expressions in Unno *et al.* (1979) indicate that the convective Cowling mechanism, while operating, is insignificant for Jovian planet oscillations.

One final internal source of stellar oscillations is believed to be coupling with turbulent convection (Unno *et al.* 1979). Since there is as yet no satisfactory theory of convection, estimates of mode excitation by this mechanism are very difficult to make. One definite result, however, is that the strongest coupling is for modes where $\sigma\tau \sim 1$, where τ is a representative convective timescale. The

most thorough investigation of convective excitation is by Goldreich and Kumar (1988). They estimated the energy E contained in acoustic modes of frequency σ in equilibrium with “turbulent pseudo-convection”:

$$\begin{aligned} E(\sigma) &\sim \rho_0 h^3 c^2 && \text{for } \sigma\tau_h \lesssim 1, \\ E(\sigma) &\sim \rho_0 h^3 c^2 (\sigma\tau_h)^{-13/2} && \text{for } 1 \lesssim \sigma\tau_h \lesssim \mathcal{M}^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

Here h is the size of the largest eddies, ρ_0 is the density, $\mathcal{M}$ is the mach number for eddy velocity v_h , and the eddy lifetime $\tau_h \sim h/v_h$ where the modes are driven. Note that the energy per mode falls off rapidly when the product $\sigma\tau_h \gtrsim 1$.

These results may be used to place a rough upper limit to the total velocity amplitude of oscillation modes excited by this convection mechanism. Assume that modes are excited by turbulence at a level in the planet where the density is ρ_{ex} and that they are observed where the density is ρ_{obs} . To calculate the total mode velocity V_p we use the Goldreich and Kumar expression, $dN/d\sigma \sim \sigma^2 c^{-3} \mathcal{V}$, for the number of modes per unit frequency in volume $\mathcal{V}$ and set the kinetic energy of all oscillation modes observed at ρ_{obs} equal to the energy added at ρ_{ex} :

$$\rho_{\text{obs}} V_p^2 \sim \int E(\sigma) \sigma^2 c^{-3} d\sigma. \quad (2.24)$$

V_p is the observed sum of the root mean square velocity amplitudes of all excited modes. Integrating (2.24) over all possible oscillation frequencies we derive

$$V_p^2 \sim \frac{\rho_{\text{obs}} v_h^3}{\rho_{\text{ex}} 2c}. \quad (2.25)$$

The most uncertain term in Equation 2.25 is the convective velocity of the largest eddies, v_h . In contrast, the sound speed in the deep interior of Jupiter or Saturn is fairly well constrained, $c \sim 1.5 \times 10^6 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$, and near the tropopause $c \sim 6.7 \times 10^4 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. An approximate value for v_h may be found by using mixing

length theory and assuming that the mixing length is comparable to the pressure scale height (Podolak *et al.* 1990):

$$v_h \approx 0.1 \left(\frac{F_{\text{conv}}}{\rho} \right)^{1/3}. \quad (2.26)$$

The convective heat flux in Saturn, F_{conv} , is approximately equal to the total internal heat flux of $2000 \text{ erg cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$; a typical interior density is 1 g cm^{-3} . Convective velocities in the deep interior are thus expected to be about 1 cm s^{-1} . At the tropopause $\rho \sim 2.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ g cm}^{-3}$ and $v_h \sim 40 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$.

The low degree f-modes propagate in the deep interior of Saturn, hence $\rho_{\text{obs}} \sim 1 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$. Considering excitation by deep seated convection and using Equation 2.25 we see that total mode velocities of about $10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ are expected. This total mode amplitude must then be divided among those modes which couple to this convection. The eddy lifetime τ_h in the deep interior, however, is approximately 10 years. The product $\sigma\tau_h \sim 10^4$ is thus orders of magnitude larger than 1 for all oscillation modes, implying that the energy from deep seated convection cannot excite modes of any period due to the rapid cutoff in Equation 2.23. In fact if values appropriate to Saturn's interior are applied to (2.23), the predicted energy per mode is about 15 orders of magnitude smaller than that needed for the 2f mode to have a 1 meter amplitude. Convection in the deep interior is an unlikely excitation mechanism for the f-modes.

Closer to the tropopause, however, convective turnover times reach the range of 1000 minutes, implying $\sigma\tau_h \sim 10$ and more efficient coupling. Unfortunately at this point the ratio $\rho_{\text{ex}}/\rho_{\text{obs}}$ is about 10^{-5} and $V_p \sim 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for the f-modes. The situation for high degree p-modes which propagate only in the atmosphere is more favorable since the density ratio is about 1 and $V_p \sim 0.5 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. For

the sun, the ratio between average individual mode velocities and V_p is about 4×10^{-4} . If a similar ratio applies to Saturn, then individual p-mode velocities would be expected to be $\lesssim 2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ and the f-modes $\lesssim 4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. In comparison, for a 200 min f-mode to have a 10 cm amplitude, a mode velocity of about $3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ is required. Thus while more favorable, upper atmospheric excitation of the f-modes also seems to fall short. It should be noted that if the convective velocities in Saturn's atmosphere are an order of magnitude larger than assumed here, *i.e.* closer to those of Jupiter (Gierasch 1976), then convection would couple efficiently to the f-modes and only the f-modes ($\sigma_{21}\tau_h \sim 1$). In this case f-modes with amplitudes of several centimeters (energies of 10^{24} ergs) could indeed be driven.

Dolginov and Muslimov (1984), using a different theory, also considered oscillation mode excitation by coupling with turbulence. Unlike Goldreich and Kumar, they modeled an actual convecting spherical planet or star. They predicted average mode velocities for Jupiter and Saturn at $\lesssim 10^{-2} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$ for well coupled modes. They also concluded that upper atmosphere convection could drive deeply seated oscillation modes. These results are similar to those reached above for the larger convective velocity. Both approaches agree that a Saturn with a vigorously convecting upper atmosphere does seem marginally capable of driving f-mode oscillations with interesting amplitudes.

The lack of a rigorous theory for convection seriously hampers both of these mode amplitude estimates. Until the theory of convection is further advanced, it is unlikely that firmer conclusions may be drawn about expected oscillation mode amplitudes.

For completeness, a more speculative oscillation excitation mechanism should be mentioned. The field of stellar nonradial oscillations was originally inspired by questions regarding stability of close binary stars. If the orbital period of one member of the binary was equal to a natural frequency of the other member, the second star might be catastrophically destroyed. Fortunately for Saturn, no significant satellite has a period close to a natural oscillation period. Tidal energy still, however, might be transferred from the tidal bulge of the planet into oscillation modes by various non-linear wave interactions (Stevenson, personal communication). Resonant interactions between waves are important in the Earth's oceans (McComas and Bretherton 1977) and atmosphere (Yeh and Liu 1970). Such interactions would take place on Saturn if the sum or difference of two oscillation frequencies were equal to a tidal forcing frequency. The equality must be near exact, with deviation of order Q^{-1} , where Q is the quality factor of the oscillations. Furthermore the wavevectors of the oscillation modes and the tidal bulge must have a vector sum or difference of zero (McComas and Bretherton 1977). Such nonlinear interactions are, however, efficient at transferring energy from low to high frequency modes (Goldreich and Kumar 1988) as would be required for this mechanism to be effective.

The two satellites of Saturn which produce the largest tidal bulges are Titan (2.4 m) and Tethys (0.9 m). It is relatively easy to find two oscillation modes of the planet, one of special interest such as an f-mode and one other mode, whose difference frequency is close ($\pm 5\%$) to a tidal frequency of one of the major satellites. Whether there are any such correspondences at an accuracy of one part in 10^5 or better is currently unknowable since the oscillation frequencies cannot be calculated that accurately. Podolak *et al.* (1990) have suggested that excitation of acoustic

oscillation of Uranus might help explain the anomalously low tidal Q of Uranus. Whether or not the oscillation modes could efficiently “steal” energy from a meter tall tidal bulge to excite one meter oscillations depends both on the Q of the tides and the Q of the oscillations. Given the great uncertainties inherent in this excitation mechanism, I do not further consider it here.

In summary, no classical method of acoustic mode excitation is unquestionably able to excite even 1 cm amplitude oscillations on Saturn. Convection, which suffers from being the least well developed theory, comes closest. The disparity between interesting amplitudes and those predicted by the Goldreich and Kumar theory is only a few orders of magnitude; there is no disparity when convective velocities slightly larger than those estimated by Equation 2.26 are considered. Since the excitation theory is still poorly developed and has yet to be rigorously tested, even on the sun, it seems prudent to search for oscillation modes on Saturn. As will be illustrated in Chapter 5, even amplitudes of a few tens of centimeters can produce observable consequences in the rings.

CHAPTER 3

OSCILLATIONS AND RING DYNAMICS

This chapter explores the way in which Saturn's rings may act as a seismograph, recording perturbations in the gravitational field of the planet produced by the acoustic oscillations. In doing so the notation of two usually disparate fields must be merged. The result is a hybrid notation that may not be instantly recognized by practitioners of either discipline.

3.1 External Gravitational Field Perturbation

Non-radial Saturnian oscillations create a density perturbation inside the planet ρ' given by

$$\rho'(r, \theta, \varphi) = \rho'(r) Y_l^m(\theta, \varphi) e^{-i\sigma t}. \quad (3.1)$$

Unlike the pressure perturbation $p'(r)$, $\rho'(r)$ is not a direct result of the oscillation eigenfrequency calculation. For adiabatic oscillations, however, the expression is just

$$\rho' = \Gamma^{-1} \frac{p'}{p} \rho. \quad (3.2)$$

It is this density perturbation which is then responsible for the perturbation to the external gravitation field of the planet.

To describe the external gravitational field of planets, I follow a variation on the notation of Zharkov and Trubitsyn (1978) who make use of the harmonics J_l , C_{lm} , and S_{lm} . The total external gravitational field Φ_e is

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_e = \frac{GM}{r} \left\{ 1 - \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^l J_l P_l(\cos \theta) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^l \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^l P_l^m(\cos \theta) [C_{lm} \cos m\varphi + S_{lm} \sin m\varphi] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

The notation is the same as in Chapter 2, with a being the equatorial radius to which the harmonics are normalized. For a fluid planet in hydrostatic equilibrium there should be no permanent non-axisymmetric terms in the potential, thus C_{lm} and S_{lm} are presumed zero for Saturn. The harmonics J_l for Saturn are listed in Table 1.1. To adapt this notation to time variable density perturbations I create the new variables $J'_l(t)$, $C'_{lm}(t)$, and $S'_{lm}(t)$. The perturbed external gravitational field Φ'_e is then

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi'_e(t) = \frac{GM}{r} \left\{ - \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^l J'_l P_l(\cos \theta) \right. \\ \left. + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \sum_{m=1}^l \left(\frac{a}{r}\right)^l P_l^m(\cos \theta) [C'_{lm} \cos m\varphi + S'_{lm} \sin m\varphi] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

The gravitational harmonics are defined as in the static case, except that integrals are taken over the density perturbation ρ' instead of the unperturbed density ρ :

$$Ma^l J'_l = - \int \rho'(\mathbf{r}) r^l P_l(\cos \theta) r^2 d\theta d\varphi dr, \quad (3.5)$$

$$Ma^l C'_{lm} = \frac{2(l-m)!}{(l+m)!} \int \rho'(\mathbf{r}) r^l P_l^m(\cos \theta) \cos m\varphi r^2 \sin \theta d\theta d\varphi dr, \quad (3.6)$$

and

$$Ma^l S'_{lm} = \frac{2(l-m)!}{(l+m)!} \int \rho'(\mathbf{r}) r^l P_l^m(\cos \theta) \sin m\varphi r^2 \sin \theta d\theta d\varphi dr. \quad (3.7)$$

When Equation (3.1) is inserted and the appropriate angular integrals calculated, these equations reduce to

$$Ma^l J'_l = - \left(\frac{4\pi}{2l+1}\right)^{1/2} e^{i\sigma_{l0n}t} \int_0^a \rho'_{ln}(r) r^{l+2} dr \quad (3.8)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} Ma^l C'_{lm} = (-1)^{(m+|m|)/2} \left(\frac{4\pi}{2l+1}\right)^{1/2} \left[\frac{(l-|m|)!}{(l+|m|)!} \right]^{1/2} \\ \times e^{i\sigma_{lmn}t} \int_0^a \rho'_{ln}(r) r^{l+2} dr. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

S'_{lm} may be caused to vanish by an appropriate choice of phase and is thus neglected. Because of the orthogonality of the spherical harmonics, only the spherical harmonic Y_l^0 contributes to term J'_l . Similarly only the Y_l^m harmonic contributes to C'_{lm} . This is a very useful result since it means that each individual oscillation mode (characterized by l , m , and n) only contributes to a single perturbed gravitational harmonic (characterized by l , $|m|$). Modes of the same l and m , but different n , *e.g.* various $l = 2$, $m = 2$ p-modes, have different frequencies and eigenfunctions which produce various C'_{lm} with differing amplitudes and frequencies. Note that the $m = 0$ modes produce an azimuthally symmetric perturbation similar to a time varying J_l term.

3.2 Resonance Conditions

The theory of satellite resonances in Saturn's rings is well established and I shall not discuss it in depth here except to cite well known results. The resonance notation will generally follow that used by Rosen (1989). This section will explain how this theory is adapted from the case of a satellite perturbing the rings to the planetary nonradial oscillations.

The gravitational potential produced by a satellite, small compared to that of Saturn, is typically Fourier-decomposed in time and angle to produce terms proportional to

$$\text{Re} \left[\phi_S(r, z) e^{i(\omega t - m\varphi)} \right] \quad (3.10)$$

where ϕ_S refers to the perturbing potential of the satellite. In this case the perturbing frequency ω is a linear combination of the natural orbital (Ω_S), epicyclic (κ_S), and vertical (μ_S) frequencies of the satellite: $\omega = m\Omega_S + k\kappa_S + p\mu_S$, where m , k , and p are integers ≥ 0 . For a given satellite, each term (like 3.10) in the expansion

of the perturbation potential is characterized by a different ω and in this sense is equivalent to a single planetary nonradial oscillation mode. Note that in the oscillation notation modes exist for $m < 0$. In the next section I will demonstrate that such modes cannot produce resonances in the rings and thus the ring resonance nomenclature which requires m , the azimuthal wave number of the perturbation, to be greater than or equal to zero is directly applicable.

A pattern frequency, the angular speed of the frame in which a given Fourier component is stationary, may be defined as $\Omega_p = \omega/m$. In the case of planetary oscillations, it is given by:

$$\Omega_p = \frac{\sigma_{lmn}}{m}. \quad (3.11)$$

The pattern frequency should not be confused with the planetary rotation frequency Ω_p . Also recall that σ_{lmn} is the oscillation frequency as seen from an inertial frame. Thus the rotation of the planet is already accounted for. The forcing frequency felt by a particle moving with orbital angular velocity Ω is $m(\Omega - \Omega_p)$. Lindblad resonances, the most important type in Saturn's rings, occur where the forcing frequency equals κ ; vertical resonances occur where the forcing frequency equals μ :

$$m\Omega_p = m\Omega(r_L) \mp \kappa(r_L), \quad \text{Lindblad}, \quad (3.12)$$

$$m\Omega_p = m\Omega(r_V) \mp \mu(r_V), \quad \text{Vertical}. \quad (3.13)$$

In each case the upper sign corresponds to an inner resonance and the lower sign to an outer resonance. Inner resonances form closer to the planet than outer resonances. Another type of resonance, a corotation resonance, occurs when the

Table 3.1

Orbital Frequency Expansion Coefficients¹

$2n$	A_{2n}	B_{2n}	C_{2n}
2	3/2	-3/2	9/2
4	-15/8	45/8	-75/8
6	35/16	-175/16	245/16
8	-315/128	2205/128	-2835/128
10	693/256	-6237/256	7623/256
12	-3003/1024	33033/1024	-39039/1024

¹Nicholson and Porco 1988, Table I.

pattern frequency Ω_p is equal to the orbital frequency of ring particles Ω . When evaluated in Saturn's equatorial plane these frequencies are given by

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \Omega^2(r) \\ \kappa^2(r) \\ \mu^2(r) \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{GM_S}{r^3} \left[1 + \sum_{l=1}^{\infty} \begin{Bmatrix} A_{2l} \\ B_{2l} \\ C_{2l} \end{Bmatrix} J_{2l} \left(\frac{a}{r} \right)^{2l} \right]. \quad (3.14)$$

The coefficients A_{2l} , B_{2l} , and C_{2l} are listed in Table 3.1. Note that the combination of Table 3.1 and Equation (3.14) imply that while the three frequencies are nearly equal, $\kappa < \Omega < \mu$.

Since Saturn's potential is nearly spherical, $\Omega \sim \kappa \sim \mu$. The condition for resonance is then approximately

$$\frac{\Omega(r_{L,V})}{\Omega_p} \approx \frac{m}{m \mp 1}. \quad (3.15)$$

Resonances which satisfy this condition are known as 'first order resonances'. This result may be generalized so that the denominator contains not $m \mp 1$, but rather $m \mp q$ where q is an arbitrary positive integer. Resonances where $q = 2$ are referred to as second order resonances, and so forth with increasing q . In Equations (3.12) and (3.13), q enters as a coefficient for κ and μ . In the case of satellites, resonances

where $q \neq 1$ produce a much smaller perturbation in the rings than first order resonances and are generally unimportant. This is because the resonant ring particles are being driven not at their fundamental epicyclic (or vertical) frequency, but at a harmonic. Second order oscillation mode resonances are also expected to be weak, but their positions will be briefly investigated in Chapter 5.

For cases in which $m = 0$ or $m \mp 1 = 0$, Equation (3.15) is not relevant and the non-spherical nature of Saturn's gravitational field must be considered. For oscillation modes with $m = 0$ there are corotation resonances where σ_{ln} equals κ or μ , depending on whether l is even or odd, respectively. There are two final special cases. When $m = 1$ there is an inner Lindblad resonance where $\Omega_p = \Omega - \kappa = \dot{\omega}$ which corresponds to a period of days. There is a similar inner vertical resonance with the nodal precession rate. For $m = 1$ the outer resonances may be found through Equation (3.12).

3.3 Allowed Oscillation Resonances

While I have defined all possible resonances between Saturnian oscillation modes and ring orbits, in reality only a very few of these resonances are actually possible. First of all an oscillation mode of degree l and order m will not produce both a vertical and a Lindblad resonance through Equations (3.12) and (3.13). For oscillation modes where $l + m$ is odd, there is no azimuthally varying component to the gravitational field at the equator, a situation required for Lindblad resonances. Similarly for $l + m$ even, the vertical gradient of the time varying gravitational field is zero at the equator and vertical motions will not be induced in the ring particles. Hence a given oscillation mode is capable of producing either a vertical or a Lindblad type resonance.

A second limitation on possible resonances is found by consideration of Saturnian oscillation periods. The longest expected oscillation periods measured in a frame rotating with the planet is about 200 min (Vorontsov 1981). The results of the next chapter agree with this value. Since the rotation period of Saturn is close to 10 hours, all oscillation modes with $m < 0$ will have negative pattern frequencies. In other words, the rotation of Saturn is sufficiently slow that waves travelling retrograde will never be carried prograde by the rotation of the planet. It is not possible to have a resonance between a prograde travelling ring particle and a retrograde pattern frequency. This justifies the statement in the previous section that negative m modes may be neglected. The single possible exception would be for the vertical resonance $-\Omega_p = \mu - \Omega = -\dot{\Omega}$. But like the apsidal precession rate, the nodal precession rate has a frequency lower than any reasonable pattern frequency. The inescapable conclusion is that nonradial oscillations with order $m < 0$ do not produce resonances in Saturn's rings.

Finally an even tighter practical limit may be placed on the number of first order resonances which might be found in the rings. Reprising Equation (3.15), at a resonance, the orbital frequency of ring particles must be approximately

$$\Omega(r_{L,V}) \approx \frac{m}{m \mp 1} \Omega_p. \quad (3.16)$$

The inner edge of Saturn's C-ring is at about 74,500 km while the outer edge of the A-ring is at about 136,800 km. This corresponds to an orbital frequency range of about 3×10^{-4} to 1×10^{-4} . As will be seen in Chapter 5, pattern frequencies for low degree Saturnian f-modes are near 3×10^{-4} when $m = l$. For $0 < m < l$, frequencies are higher, approaching 6×10^{-4} . From even these few values it should be clear that when the minus sign is chosen in Equation (3.18), *i.e.* when ILR's are considered, the resonance radii are moved inward, away from

the inner C-ring. When the positive sign is chosen, resonance radii move into the rings. Thus generally speaking it is outer Lindblad or vertical resonances which should be expected; inner resonances will lie well inside of the C-ring. Furthermore only the $m = l$ modes generally have pattern frequencies low enough to resonate in the C-ring. Even when accounting for the coefficient in Equation (3.16), modes with $m < l$ will have a hard time producing resonances in the rings because of their higher frequencies. Corotation radii for orders $m = l$ will lie near the C-ring inner edge. Finally the higher radial order p-modes have much higher frequencies and will not produce appropriate pattern frequencies. While all possibilities will be investigated in Chapter 5, the expectation is that only Outer Lindblad Resonances (OLR) produced by f-modes of order $m = l$ and perhaps some Outer Vertical Resonances (OVR) produced by modes of order $m = l - 1$ are likely to found in the C-ring.

While Saturn may resonate in a multitudinous number of different oscillation modes with varying frequencies, consideration of orbital mechanics and the approximate oscillation frequencies has ruled out most modes from playing any significant role in the rings. There are only ~ 9 oscillation modes of degree $l \leq 10$ which meet all of the requirements set out in this section. While all possibilities will be investigated, it is a useful result that most oscillation modes do not produce resonances. If there were many possible resonances, it would be very difficult conclude that any single ring feature is produced by any particular hypothetical resonance.

3.4 Ring Response at Resonance

The way in which the rings respond to various types of resonant forcing has important observational consequences. Typically, weak resonances do not produce any observable perturbations to the rings. Stronger resonances launch waves which may be observable in various occultation measurements or in Voyager images of the rings. Finally very strong resonances can produce gaps in the rings. To determine which features might be seen in the rings at resonances produced by planetary oscillations, it is necessary to examine the strength of the resonances.

The strength of a resonance is characterized by the torque T that it applies on the rings. The linear torque produced at an OLR is

$$T^L = -\frac{m\pi^2}{3(m+1)}(2m+l+1)^2 \left[\frac{\Sigma}{\Omega^2} \Phi_e'^2 \right]_{r_L}. \quad (3.17)$$

The only new variable is Σ , the surface mass density of the ring. The potential perturbation Φ_e' is taken from Equation 3.4, neglecting the time variation which has already been applied in deriving (3.17). In an empirical study of wave and gap features in the C-ring, Rosen (1989) found that resonances with T^L/Σ less than about $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ s}^{-2}$ do not produce features detectable in the radio science occultation data. Stronger resonances with $1 \times 10^{13} \lesssim T^L/\Sigma \lesssim 1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ s}^{-2}$ produce detectable wave features. Finally resonances with larger torques seem to produce gaps with embedded ringlets. This production of a gap plus embedded ringlet by a single resonance is still not perfectly understood. Although it is possible that after a strong resonance clears a gap, sufficiently large particles may be left behind to shepherd any remaining material into a narrow ring (Porco *et al.* 1984). Rather than investigate all ring theories or attempt to derive theoretical wave

production requirements, I will simply use Rosen's (1989) empirical C-ring torque requirements.

The variety of resonance (OVR or OLR) determines both the type of wave launched and the direction in which it propagates. At Lindblad resonances density waves are produced. At vertical resonances bending waves are launched. In the case of Lindblad resonances, waves propagate away from the planet at inner resonances and towards the planet at outer resonances. The opposite holds true for bending waves. A unique propagation direction may be determined since the wavelength of a wave decreases away from resonance. The Voyager radio science subsystem (RSS) occultation data alone, however, cannot discriminate between a bending wave and a density wave. Thus a wave which is observed to be propagating away from Saturn in the RSS data is either a density wave launched at an inner Lindblad resonance (ILR) or a bending wave produced by an outer vertical resonance (OVR). As discussed in Section 3.3, one would expect to find outer Lindblad resonances from planetary oscillation modes in the C-ring. The wave signature of these resonances is thus expected to be a wave propagating inwards, towards the planet. Figure 3.1 compares the type of waves produced by an external satellite and a planetary oscillation mode.

Finally waves launched at resonances appear in the form of spirals, tightly wound around the planet. Wave theory predicts that the number of spiral arms is equal to the azimuthal wave number m of the perturbing potential (Shu 1984). This property is also a useful diagnostic since resonances predicted by planetary oscillation modes will each have a unique value of m . Some constraints on the number of spiral arms of waves observed in the C-ring have been determined (Rosen 1989).

Figure 3.1 The cartoon on the left illustrates a density wave launched in the rings by a satellite. The resonance is an Inner Lindblad Resonance (ILR) and is located at the point where there is a comensurability between the natural frequencies of the satellite and ring particles. The cartoon on the right illustrates a density wave launched in the rings by an oscillation mode. The resonance is an Outer Lindblad Resonance (OLR) and is located at the point where there is a comensurability between the natural frequencies of the ring particles and the pattern frequency of the travelling sectoral mode. Notice the difference in direction of propagation of the two density waves.

The perturbation in the rings produced by corotation resonances is more difficult to detect. Corotation resonances produce azimuthal variations in the ring density at the resonant radius. Future experiments which produce multiple occultation cuts through the ring will be more useful for searching for perturbations at corotation resonances and allow the azimuthal structure of the ring to be compared at various locations.

3.5 Unexplained C-Ring Features

Because of its relatively low optical depth, the C-ring is well suited to RSS occultation analysis. Rosen (1989) has analyzed the Voyager RSS occultation data for the C-ring and compiled a list of “clearly identifiable” wave features which are not correlated with known satellite resonances. The eight C-ring wave features are listed in Table 3.2. In six of these waves the wave amplitude decreases towards Saturn, indicating that these waves are produced at either outer Lindblad or inner vertical resonances. The other two waves each must be produced at either an ILR or OVR. Limits on the number of spiral arms for these features as derived by Rosen (1989) are also listed. Also listed for each wave is a crude measure of the wave amplitude $\delta\tau/\tau_n$ near the wave origin. The maximum wave amplitude in units of the radio science opacity is $\delta\tau$, the average opacity across the entire wave is τ_n (Rosen 1989, Table 21).

Gaps with embedded ringlets are also a common C-ring feature. Table 3.3 describes the only significant gap or gap-ringlet feature in the C-ring that is not associated with a known resonance. To qualify as a gap-ringlet pair, the radio opacity must drop to zero and the ringlet must have sharp edges and be optically thick (Rosen 1989). Several gaps and ringlets inside of about 76,000 km are unexplained,

Table 3.2Unexplained C-Ring Wave Features¹

Radial Location (km)	τ_n	$\delta\tau/\tau_n$	m	Wave Type
74945	0.167	0.7	2-3	OVR/ILR
80990	0.231	0.7	3-11	IVR/OLR
82065	0.295	1.6	2-4	IVR/OLR
82211	0.221	1.3	2-5	IVR/OLR
83638	0.169	0.7	3-8	IVR/OLR
84650	0.205	0.6	2-5	IVR/OLR
85465	0.132	2.0	1-2	IVR/OLR ²
85690	0.309	1.8	1-3	OVR/ILR ²

¹Rosen 1989. ²If $m > 1$.**Table 3.3**Unexplained C-Ring Gap/Ringlet Feature^{1,2}

Feature	Radial Location (km)
Maxwell Gap	
INNER EDGE	87322
OUTER EDGE	87590
Maxwell Ringlet	
INNER EDGE	87459
OUTER EDGE	87523

¹Rosen 1989. ²Data from Porco *et al.* 1984.

but these are too minor to consider here. There are no other gaps or gap-ringlet pairs in the C-ring that cannot be explained by a resonance with a known satellite (Rosen 1989).

The Maxwell gap and embedded ringlet (at 87500 km) is thus the only gap-ringlet feature in the C-ring which is not associated with a resonance stronger

than the Mimas 4:1 ILR (Rosen 1989). This particular Mimas resonance ($T^L/\Sigma = -1.15 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ s}^{-2}$) produces a density wave. The Prometheus 2:1 resonance ($T^L/\Sigma = -8.11 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^4 \text{ s}^{-2}$) falls within a gap at 88714 km but its dynamic association with this gap and its embedded ringlet is debated (Porco and Nicholson 1987; Rosen 1989). The Maxwell gap is much wider than this putative Prometheus gap (260 vs. 50 km) and the embedded ringlet is also wider (64 vs. 40 km). There are three other resonances in the C-ring which seem to be associated with either a ringlet embedded in a gap or a ringlet adjacent to a gap (Rosen 1989).

The total set of significant unexplained waves or gaps in the C-ring thus consists of 1 gap-ringlet pair, 6 OLR/IVR type waves, and 2 OVR/ILR type waves. Since, as will be fully demonstrated in Chapter 5, resonances with oscillation modes of the planet produce only resonances in the C-ring, it is these features which wait to be explained by planetary oscillation modes.

CHAPTER 4

OSCILLATION CALCULATIONS

This chapter concerns the implementation and application of the oscillation theory presented in Chapter 2 to Saturn. Important details of the eigenfrequency calculation are presented as well as the frequencies calculated for various models.

4.1 Eigenvalue Calculation

The eigenvalue differential equations (Eqs. 2.5 – 2.7) may be recast as four first-order differential equations with four dimensionless variables (Unno *et al.* 1979).

The variables are

$$y_1 = \frac{\xi_r}{r}, \quad (4.1)$$

$$y_2 = \frac{1}{gr} \left(\frac{p'}{\rho} + \Phi' \right), \quad (4.2)$$

$$y_3 = \frac{1}{gr} \Phi', \quad (4.3)$$

and

$$y_4 = \frac{1}{g} \frac{d\Phi'}{dr}. \quad (4.4)$$

The independent variable

$$x = r/R \quad (4.5)$$

is used to replace r . The resulting four equations (Unno *et al.* 1979; eqs. 17.14 – 17.17) are as follows:

$$x \frac{dy_1}{dx} = (V_g - 3)y_1 + \left[\frac{l(l+1)}{c_1\omega^2} - V_g \right] y_2 + V_g y_3, \quad (4.6)$$

$$x \frac{dy_2}{dx} = (c_1\omega^2 - A^*)y_1 + (A^* - U + 1)y_2 - A^*y_3, \quad (4.7)$$

$$x \frac{dy_3}{dx} = (1 - U)y_3 + y_4, \quad (4.8)$$

and

$$x \frac{dy_4}{dx} = UA^*y_1 + UV_g y_2 + [l(l+1) - UV_g]y_3 - Uy_4. \quad (4.9)$$

The dimensionless quantities are

$$V_g = -\frac{1}{\Gamma} \frac{d \ln p}{d \ln r} = \frac{gr}{c^2}, \quad (4.10)$$

$$U \equiv \frac{d \ln M_r}{d \ln r} = \frac{4\pi \rho r^3}{M_r}, \quad (4.11)$$

$$c_1^{-1} \equiv (M_r/M)/(r/R)^3, \quad (4.12)$$

$$\omega^2 = \sigma^2 R^3 / (GM), \quad (4.13)$$

and

$$A^* \equiv -rA = rg^{-1}N^2. \quad (4.14)$$

The new terms are M_r , the mass enclosed in radius r and the Schwarzschild discriminant

$$A = \frac{d \ln \rho}{dr} - \frac{1}{\Gamma} \frac{d \ln p}{dr}. \quad (4.15)$$

The other terms are defined in Section 2.3. Note that the definition of c_1 is corrected from an error in Unno *et al.* (1979) and that the quantities on the right of the last equal sign in both Equations 4.10 and 4.14 are correct only for a non-rotating planet. The next section will discuss how the dimensionless quantities as a function of radius are computed from a Saturn model.

The dimensionless boundary conditions (Unno *et al.* 1979; eqs. 17.29, 17.30, 17.46, and 17.49) are

$$\frac{c_1 \omega^2}{l} y_1 - y_2 = 0 \quad (4.15)$$

and

$$ly_3 - y_4 = 0 \quad (4.16)$$

at $r = 0$ and

$$(l + 1)y_3 + y_4 = 0 \quad (4.17)$$

and

$$y_1 - y_2 + y_3 = 0 \quad (4.18)$$

at $r = R$. Equations 4.6 – 4.9 combined with these boundary conditions and the normalization $y_1 = 1$ at $r = R$ comprise the dimensionless eigenvalue problem.

There are several approaches to numerically solve an eigenvalue problem such as this one. I chose to use a relaxation technique described by Press *et al.* (1986; Section 16.3) because of its flexibility and ease of modification. In this technique the four ordinary differential equations are replaced by four finite difference equations which are solved on an evenly spaced grid of points. The relaxation method proceeds by iteratively improving on a first guess of the solution. When the solution has converged, the eigenfunctions y_1 through y_4 and the square of the oscillation frequency ω are written to a file. The convergence criterion used was that eigenfunction correction averaged over all nodes be less than 10^{-6} . Most models could meet this criterion in 7 to 8 iterations or less. Some models, however, had difficulty meeting this requirement after 20 iterations and a few results were accepted with a standard an order of magnitude less restrictive.

A word about the choice of grid spacing is now in order. Many investigators in the field of stellar oscillations use a variable grid where the density of grid points is greater in regions where the eigenfunctions are most variable, typically near the surface. I did not use this technique for two reasons. First f-modes have no

radial nodes in the fluid displacement eigenfunction and are thus generally smooth everywhere, they are not more variable near the surface. Secondly the Saturn models used are more or less empirical density distributions and are created on a grid spaced equally in radius. The outer 10% of the planet is really no better understood than any other portion and increasing the number of grid points in that region would add little or no additional information. Producing more grid points in a theoretical stellar model, in contrast, is straightforward. In any event, as demonstrated below, acceptable accuracy in low to intermediate degree oscillation modes was achieved using the chosen grid.

Other than the dimensionless quantities describing the planetary model and the eigenfunction guesses (the accuracy of which, in practice, are relatively unimportant), the degree of oscillation l and the initial frequency guess ω^2 must be provided for each oscillation mode calculation. Using these parameters the computer program finds an eigensolution which satisfies all the constraints. By counting the number of nodes in the resultant radial displacement eigenfunction y_1 , the radial order of the computed eigenfunction could be determined, uniquely establishing the identity of the eigenmode. For example, if degree $l = 3$ was specified and $y_1(r)$ has 4 zero crossings, then the calculated eigenmode is the $l = 3$, $n = 4$ p-mode non-radial oscillation of Saturn. With practice it became relatively straightforward to specify the correct ω^2 to produce the desired result. But, given the nature of the relaxation method, the exact mode arrived at by the computer could not be known with certainty until the y_1 eigenfunction was examined. Occasionally the method could not converge, necessitating a change in the initial guess of either

Table 4.1

Polytrope Nonradial Oscillation Frequencies ω^2
 Comparison to Earlier Results, $\Gamma = 5/3$

mode	ν					
	1		1.5		3*	
	prior	this work	prior	this work	prior	this work
$2p_6$	129.9†	129.7	—	119.9	109.9†	109.3
$2p_2$	23.49	23.48	23.52‡	23.51	29.36	29.29
$2p_1$	9.308	9.304	10.29	10.29	17.37	17.36
$2f$	1.498	1.501	2.119	2.120	9.480	9.473
$3f$	—	2.869	—	3.742	9.867§	9.857
$5f$	—	5.310	—	6.333	10.27§	10.27

* This index only, $\Phi' = 0$. † Results of Robe 1968. ‡ Results of Cox 1980.
 § Results of Kopal 1949. — None available.

the eigenfrequency or eigenfunctions. In all cases discussed in subsequent sections, however, all eigenmodes of interest could be calculated.

To demonstrate that the non-radial oscillation problem had been appropriately modeled and the relaxation technique was giving valid results, numerous polytropic models were used as test cases. A polytropic star is one for which the pressure-density relation

$$p = K\rho^{1+\frac{1}{\nu}} \quad (4.19)$$

holds. The variable ν is known as the polytropic index of the star. Saturn and especially Jupiter may be crudely approximated as $\nu = 1$ polytropes. Table 4.1 compares the results of oscillation eigenfrequency calculations using the technique from this chapter with results of other investigators. In all cases, for a variety of polytropic indices and oscillation degrees, the agreement is excellent. It should be noted that early workers in the field often made the assumption that $\Phi'(r) = 0$.

Table 4.2

Polytrope Nonradial Oscillation Frequencies ω^2
 Dependence on N for $\nu = 1$, $\Gamma = 5/3$

mode	N			Robe†
	101	301	1001	
$2p_2$	23.26	23.46	23.48	23.49
$2p_1$	9.276	9.302	9.304	9.308
$2f$	1.493	1.497	1.501	1.498
$5p_2$	38.42	39.05	39.15	—
$5p_1$	18.83	18.96	18.98	—
$5f$	5.296	5.305	5.310	—

†Robe 1968; N not stated.

This assumption, known as the Cowling approximation, is approximately true and can significantly increase the speed, but not the accuracy, of the calculation. Calculations in this thesis do not employ the Cowling approximation except where noted in Table 4.1. There the approximation is used in order to have more previous calculations with which to compare. The behavior of the fluid displacement eigenfunction $\xi(r)$ was also compared with previous calculations (Kopal 1949; Robe 1968). Agreement with radial location of nodes and amplitude variation with radius was again excellent.

The ability of the relaxation method to reproduce eigenfrequency and eigenfunction results for polytropic stars indicates that the method is indeed implemented correctly. Polytropic models have a further application, however, in testing the sensitivity of the results to changes in the number of model mesh points. Polytropic models may be easily constructed with an arbitrary number of mesh points; conventional planetary interior models are much less flexible. Table 4.2

compares normalized oscillation frequencies of a $\nu = 1$ polytrope where the number of mesh points, N , has been varied. In general, the higher overtone p-modes are more sensitive to N while the f-mode frequencies are affected only at the 0.1% level. Also the frequency difference between calculations with N of 101 and 301 is usually larger than the difference between 301 and 1001. In all cases the difference in frequency is less than 1%. Since I am primarily interested in the f-modes and since program execution time increases rapidly with number of mesh points, I generally use $N = 101$ in the Saturn calculations. Some calculations do use $N = 301$ for comparison.

4.2 Distillation of Model Parameters

For the oscillation eigenmode solution program described above to run, it must first be given the variation with radius of V_g , U , c_1 , and A^* defined by equations 4.10 – 4.12 and 4.14. The information to calculate these quantities comes principally from the output file MODEL which is produced by a Jovian planet inversion program (see Hubbard and Horedt 1983; Hubbard and Marley 1989). This section discusses how the required quantities are calculated for a particular Saturn model. Which models are chosen for consideration to begin with are discussed in Section 4.3.

It is important to stress that the file MODEL describes one possible, self-consistent density/pressure profile of a rotating Saturn. This is not the pressure/density profile Saturn would have if it did not rotate. This difficulty is overcome by using the rotating planet profiles, but normalized to the average radius. The hypothetical, non-rotating Saturn has the same pressure and density distribution as the observed Saturn, but a different radius. The first order rotation

correction (Section 2.3) accounts for rotating frame forces, while the second order correction accounts for deformation of the planetary figure. The perturbation calculation applied to non-rotating Saturn then reproduces the ‘real’ rotating Saturn interior model and oscillation frequencies. Parameters characterizing the planetary interior are referred to the average planetary radius (defined by Zharkov and Trubitsyn 1978), not the equatorial or polar radius. Furthermore these parameters must not be calculated using simplifications appropriate for a non-rotating planet, but rather from the actual pressure and density profiles for the hypothetical non-rotating planet. As long as these two procedures are followed, the parameter calculations remain internally self-consistent.

The file MODEL contains the pressure, density, enclosed mass M_r and description of figure for equally spaced points in radius of the planet. From this information alone it is straightforward to calculate the parameters U and c_1 . The terms A^* and V_g , however, also depend on $\Gamma = (d \ln p / d \ln \rho)_{\text{ad}}$. Hence the slope of an adiabat in pressure-density space with the same composition as the material at each point in the planet must be known. If Saturn were of uniform composition and fully convective, Γ could simply be calculated from the observed planetary pressure-density profile. Comparison of Saturn’s pressure-density profile with those of constant composition adiabats (Figure 4.1), however, indicates that this is probably not the case. The dashed lines in the figures are adiabats for hydrogen-helium mixtures with varying helium mass fractions, ranging from $Y = 0.06$ to 0.50 . These adiabats are calculated from the equations of state of Marley and Hubbard (1988) and Hubbard and DeWitt (1985). The solid line represents one possible Saturn model. In order to calculate the appropriate Γ at each point in the Saturn model, it is necessary to find the slope of the adiabat passing through that point of the

Figure 4.1. The solid line represents a typical Saturn interior model in pressure-density space. The core is to the right and the tropopause to the left (near $\log p = -6$). The dashed lines are various adiabats for hydrogen/helium mixtures, with helium mass fraction (Y) varying from 0.06 to 0.50. The departure of the model from the dashed lines implies that Saturn is denser at any given pressure level than would be predicted by a model with a constant composition. The equation of state interpolates between molecular and metallic hydrogen in the region near $\log \rho = 0$.

model. Using adiabats such as those illustrated in Figure 4.1 and interpolating where necessary, this is easily done.

Unfortunately there are two complications to this procedure. The first is how the departure of the Saturn model from the $Y = 0.06$ adiabat should be interpreted.

The departure might be due to a steadily rising helium abundance, as implied in Figure 4.1. The same variation, however, might instead be produced by increasing the mixing ratio of ices, as is illustrated in Figure 4.2. In this scenario the density enhancement in the planet is produced not by Y varying from 0.06 (the observed atmospheric value) to 0.50, but rather by raising the ice mass fraction from 0% to about 40%. The Γ calculated for each of these two scenarios is illustrated in Figure 4.3. For now, focus on the molecular hydrogen region where $\beta = r/R \gtrsim 0.70$. The assumption of a varying helium mass fraction (Y) produces a slightly smaller Γ than varying the ice fraction (Z). Since the correct interpretation is unknown, both scenarios must be considered when calculating oscillation frequencies. An intermediate case would lie between these two extremes.

The second problem in the calculation of Γ leaps out in Figure 4.3. The region where Γ drops to very low values is the region where Γ cannot be meaningfully calculated because of the uncertainties surrounding the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition. The pressure at which this transition occurs is believed to be between 3 and 5 Mbar (Marley and Hubbard 1988), but it is unknown whether the transition is an abrupt first-order one or a gradual continuous one. The equation of state used to create the adiabats for Figures 4.1 and 4.2 simply interpolates in the uncertain region between the molecular and metallic hydrogen regimes. While this approach is acceptable for modelling the interior structure, it clearly introduces a large uncertainty in the derivative quantity Γ . This is because the transition region falls over a significant fraction of the radius of Saturn, as is illustrated in Figure 4.3.

This difficulty is dealt with in the same manner as the compositional question. Extreme cases are identified and estimates of Γ made. The procedure is illustrated

Figure 4.2. Same as Figure 4.1, except that the adiabats represent various mixtures of hydrogen, helium, and ices. The ice mass fraction (Z) varies from 0.0 to 0.5.

in Figure 4.4 where the dashed Γ from Figure 4.3 is modified. One limiting case is for the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition to take place at high pressure, deep in the planet. In that case the low pressure Γ is simply extrapolated to a radius of $\beta \sim 0.4$ where an abrupt transition is made to the metallic hydrogen Γ (case A in the figure). The other extreme is to extrapolate the high pressure, metallic Γ to large radii and put the transition near $\beta \sim 0.6$ (case B). Still another possibility is that Γ may actually be quite depressed through a continuous transition

Figure 4.3. The lines represent calculations of the adiabatic Γ for the cases shown in Figures 4.1 and 4.2. The large troughs are produced by the equation of state interpolation region. The uncertainty due to the composition (ice or helium) may be seen in those regions where the lines diverge outside of the troughs.

(Stevenson personal communication). To model this case Γ may be simply taken as is (case 0), since there is no theory for this situation. By determining how sensitive the final computed oscillation frequencies are to these alternative interpretations, limits on the computed accuracy of eigenfrequencies are placed in the next section.

Figure 4.4. Γ calculated from the ice case in Figure 4.3 labelled '0'. Two different ways of interpolating across the trough are shown as 'A' and 'B'. These letters correspond to the codes used in Table 4.3. The primary composition of each region of the planet is also indicated.

With the above method for computing $\Gamma(r)$ it is then simple to compute $V_g(r)$ from Equation 4.10. The quantity A^* is also easily arrived at via Equations 4.14 and 4.15. Consideration of A^* , however, is further complicated by philosophical considerations. A^* is fundamentally a measure of the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, N . A gas parcel oscillates buoyantly at frequency N . If the interior of Saturn were

perfectly convecting and had a uniform composition, N would equal zero nearly exactly. Composition gradients, however, produce a positive buoyancy frequency and hence interfere with purely pressure driven oscillations. Figures 4.1 and 4.2 illustrate that such composition gradients may be present inside Saturn. Even slight composition gradients, however, could severely restrict heat transport in the planet (Podolak *et al.* 1990) and this is not observed. Thus while nominal values of A^* may be easily calculated for each treatment of Γ , another case where $A^* = 0$ throughout the planet should also be considered. In this way the importance of the detailed compositional layering within the planet can be assessed. In all cases it is assumed that $A^* = 0$ in the outermost and innermost regions of the planet and only deviates in the region $0.4 \lesssim \beta \lesssim 0.9$.

With the calculation of A^* , all the quantities required to calculate oscillation frequencies are at hand. For a given interior model, there are three choices which must be made when distilling these quantities. First, is the shape of the pressure/density profile attributable to changing helium concentration or changing ice content? Second, how is the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition to be treated? Third, is there really a composition gradient after all – how should A^* be treated? The next section considers the impact each of these choices has on the calculated oscillation frequencies for a variety of interior models.

4.3 Zeroth Order Saturnian Oscillation Calculation Results

The previous section discussed various uncertainties pertaining to the thermodynamic parameters which characterize a Saturn interior model. As discussed in Section 1.1 there are also uncertainties concerning the interior models themselves. These uncertainties combine to produce a phase space within which the

Figure 4.5. Two Saturn interior models. Model PRF assumes that the core is rock only, model 273 assumes that the core consists of an inner rocky and an outer icy layers. Models from Hubbard and Marley (1989).

real Saturn and its thermodynamic properties are assumed to lie. To investigate this phase space I have selected four interior models and several combinations of interior properties for which oscillation frequencies will be calculated. The interior models (Figure 4.5) consist of a two-layer core model (Model 273), a one-layer core model (Model PRF), and two variations on 273 where the gravitational harmonic J_4 varies across its error bar (Models 273+ and 273-). These models were selected after extensive exploratory investigations indicated that smaller model differences,

Table 4.3

Saturnian Oscillation Calculation Summary

Calculation	Model	Γ Treatment	A^*	Comment
A	273	0	= 0	see Figure 4.4
B	273	A	$\neq 0$	
C	273	A	= 0	
D	273	B	= 0	
BB	273	C	$\neq 0$	H trans. at 3 Mbar
CC	273	C	= 0	same as BB except for A^*
FF1	273	A	= 0	same as C but 301 pt. model; 101 pt. calculation
FF2	273	A	= 0	301 pt. model; 301 pt. calc.
FF3	273	A	$\neq 0$	same as FF2 except for A^*
K	273'	B	$\neq 0$	K - LL: see Fig. 4.6
KK	273'	B	= 0	273' is slight 273 variation
L	273'	A	$\neq 0$	
LL	273'	A	= 0	
J4P	273+	A	= 0	similar to 273 model except $J_4 + \Sigma$
J4M	273-	A	= 0	similar to 273 model except $J_4 - \Sigma$
F	PRF	A	= 0	H trans. at 3 Mbar
G	PRF	A	$\neq 0$	same as F except A^*
H	PRF	A	= 0	same as F but trans. at 5 Mbar
Q	PRF	C	= 0	H trans. at 5 Mbar; Γ differs from H
P	PRF	C	= 0	similar to Q except Z varies
R	PRF	C	$\neq 0$	same as P except for A^*

such as changing the interpolation region used by the model inversion program, produced virtually no detectable oscillation frequency differences. The chosen models combined with the thermodynamic uncertainties listed at the end of the previous section define the maximum uncertainty inherent in Saturnian oscillation frequency calculations.

The range of models and interior parameters investigated is summarized in Table 4.3. The adiabatic Γ treatments 0, A, and B were described in the last section.

Treatment C is basically any variation from those prescriptions, such as intermediate or extreme cases. An example is shown in Figure 4.6 where particularly large variations of Γ used in two calculations are illustrated. Other C treatments are explained in the comment section of the table. The A^* column indicates whether internal composition gradients are assumed to be non-existent ($= 0$) or as indicated by the interior model and sample adiabats ($\neq 0$). While not every possible permutation has been investigated, calculations A – R investigate each aspect of the identified Saturn uncertainty phase space. Numerous other exploratory calculations, some considering unphysical models, give confidence that a representative survey of reasonable possibilities has indeed been completed.

The zeroth order periods for nonradial oscillation modes 2f – 8f are reported in Table 4.4. Summaries of these results and a comparison with the calculations of Vorontsov *et al.* (1976) are in Table 4.5. Detailed behavior of the data will be discussed below, but several interesting results are immediately apparent. The first is the lack of great variability in the results, even when models are significantly different. Setting aside calculation A for the moment, the largest difference in oscillation periods between calculations is about 5%. Secondly, higher degree oscillation modes, which penetrate successively less deeply into the planet, are progressively less sensitive to the calculation variations. The standard deviation of all the results, excluding A, falls from 2.2% for the 2f mode to 0.2% for the 8f mode. Also the agreement with results for the 14 year old Saturn model of Vorontsov *et al.* (1976) is surprisingly good, with a maximum difference from the overall mean of about 2%, again for the 2f mode. The Vorontsov *et al.* periods are uniformly longer, however. This result may be qualitatively understood in terms of model core size, as will be discussed below.

Figure 4.6. Two extreme interpolations of Γ across the molecular/metallic hydrogen phase transition are shown.

Before further considering the calculation results, an important numerical issue needs to be covered. In calculations A – CC, planet parameters calculated from a 101 point Saturn model were applied to a 101 point grid for oscillation frequency determination. Calculation FF1 used a 301 point Saturn model to derive parameters, but still used a 101 point grid for frequency calculations. Finally calculation FF2 used 301 points throughout. Comparison of calculations C, FF1, and FF2 reveals that using a 101 point interior model introduces an error of almost 2% in

Table 4.4

Saturnian f-mode Oscillation Periods (min)

Zeroth Order

mode	A	B	C	D	BB	CC	FF1	FF2	FF3	K	KK	L	LL	J4P	J4M
2f	232.9	179.3	176.8	176.2	180.3	177.2	173.8	174.0	176.4	175.4	173.3	176.8	174.2	171.1	177.7
3f	140.7	134.5	134.9	135.0	134.8	134.9	133.7	133.8	133.6	133.6	133.8	133.5	133.7	132.4	135.5
4f	114.5	113.6	114.4	114.5	113.7	114.4	113.8	113.8	113.1	113.2	113.8	113.1	113.7	113.2	114.7
5f	101.0	100.7	101.5	101.5	100.8	101.5	101.2	101.2	100.5	100.5	101.2	100.5	101.1	100.9	101.6
6f	92.04	91.77	92.39	92.42	91.77	92.39	92.20	92.22	91.65	91.66	92.22	91.62	92.19	92.05	92.39
7f	85.28	84.98	85.48	85.50	84.98	85.47	85.38	85.40	84.94	84.94	85.40	84.92	85.38	85.33	85.45
8f	79.89	79.59	79.99	80.00	79.59	79.96	79.96	79.97	79.61	79.59	79.96	79.58	79.96	79.95	79.96

mode	F	G	H	Q	P	R
2f	173.8	176.0	173.9	174.0	173.4	175.2
3f	133.8	133.8	133.8	133.8	133.8	132.9
4f	113.9	113.5	113.9	113.9	113.9	113.0
5f	101.2	100.8	101.2	101.2	101.3	100.6
6f	92.25	92.25	92.25	92.25	92.31	91.72
7f	85.42	85.05	85.42	85.42	85.46	84.99
8f	79.98	79.66	79.98	79.98	80.01	79.63

Table 4.5

Saturnian f-mode Oscillation Periods (min)

Zeroth Order

mode	VZL ¹	All ²			273 ³			PRF ⁴		
		mean	std. dev.	%	mean	std. dev.	%	mean	std. dev.	%
2f	180	175.4	2.16	1.23	174.8	1.26	0.72	174.4	0.91	0.52
3f	138	134.0	0.73	0.54	133.7	0.10	0.08	133.7	0.34	0.25
4f	117	113.8	0.47	0.42	113.5	0.32	0.28	113.7	0.34	0.30
5f	103	101.1	0.35	0.35	100.9	0.34	0.33	101.1	0.26	0.25
6f	93.7	92.1	0.28	0.30	92.0	0.28	0.30	92.2	0.20	0.22
7f	86.4	85.3	0.22	0.26	85.2	0.23	0.27	85.3	0.23	0.23
8f	80.7	79.9	0.18	0.22	79.8	0.18	0.23	79.9	0.20	0.20

¹ Vorontsov, Zharkov, and Lubimov (1976); ² This work, models B - R; ³ This work, models FF1 - LL; ⁴ This work, models F - R. All references to order in Table 4.3.

the eigenfrequency. Once data is obtained from a 301 point interior model, however, comparison of FF1 and FF2 reveals that, as in the polytrope, the number of grid points in the eigenfrequency calculation is not important. The reason for this difference is that derivative quantities may be calculated more accurately from a 301 point interior model than a 101 point one. Thus all calculations subsequent to FF1 used a 301 point Saturn model to provide data for a 101 point eigenfrequency calculation. For this reason calculations B – CC are not included in the Model 273 summary in Table 4.5, the results are included in Table 4.4 since they do contain some useful information.

When the Tables 4.4 and 4.5 are examined it becomes apparent that the oscillation periods of the two-layer core Saturn model (Model 273) and the one-layer core model (Model PRF) are virtually identical. None of the low degree fundamental modes can reliably distinguish between the two cases. These modes, however, are much more sensitive to the variation in the gravitational harmonic J_4 , as evidenced in calculations J4P and J4M. Using a 273-like model with $J_4 = J_4 \pm \Sigma$ produces a period variation of 4%, the largest variation seen in the data, excepting model A. To understand this difference, consider Figure 4.7. The difference between models 273+ and 273- is basically the size of the core. Because the density in the outer core is 2 to 3 times that in the adjacent metallic hydrogen region, the outer core sound speed is 40 to 70% lower (recall that $c^2 = \Gamma p / \rho$). A sound wave propagating downward in the 273- model comes to the core sooner than in the 273+ model. Thus the sound wave in the 273+ model travels rapidly for a longer time in the deep interior of the planet and consequently has a shorter round trip travel time after reflection. This is why the 2f through 4f modes in the J4P calculation have significantly shorter periods than the J4M calculation. The higher degree modes

Figure 4.7. The solid line is model 273 from Figure 4.5. The dashed lines are produced by giving the planetary model inversion program values of J_4 plus and minus the one standard deviation error bar shown in Table 1.1.

do not travel as deeply into the planet and are less affected by the size of the core. Model 273 and PRF show less variation because although the cores are of different sizes, the sound speed drops even more rapidly in the denser, single layer PRF core. The net result is very little period variation. The Vorontsov *et al.* (1976) single layer core, however, is much larger than that used here. Thus one predicts longer oscillation periods for their model, which is indeed observed.

A similar sound speed effect may be observed when the adiabatic Γ is varied. For example consider the K and L calculations and Figure 4.6. In the L calculations a relatively low value of Γ is used while in the K cases a larger Γ is used. These two cases are meant to bracket variations in Γ which might take place near the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition. The L cases produce a slower sound speed and consequently the oscillation periods are longer than the comparable K calculations, but only by a minute or so. An extreme example of the same phenomenon is case A. In case A, Γ is allowed to drop to a very low value over the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition as in shown in Figure 4.4, treatment 0. This drastic lowering of the sound speed produces a major lengthening of the 2f and to a lesser extent, the 3f periods. By degree $l = 4$, however, the mode periods are indistinguishable from the other cases. This treatment of Γ is the only plausible perturbation which could be found which affected the lower degree oscillation periods more than changing the value of J_4 . Further experiments demonstrated that virtually any desired value of the 2f mode oscillation period longer than 170 min could be obtained by such major operations on the transition region sound speed. In reality, however, it is unlikely that if the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition is gradual, it takes place over several megabars of pressure in the planet. Case A then, represents a worst possible case scenario.

Lesser variations in Γ produced virtually no changes in oscillation periods. Cases C, D, and CC are similar except for details of Γ . The consequent period variations are insignificant. Likewise cases F, H, and Q show little variation. Cases B and BB are similar as are G and R. Yet one final Γ variation should be considered. As discussed in the previous section, there is an ambiguity as to what produces the density enhancement in the deep interior of Saturn: ice or helium. How this

question is answered also affects the Γ calculation throughout the planet. All of the calculations in Table 4.3 assume He is responsible, except for cases P and R. Case P should be compared to the similar Q in Table 4.4. The differences are again insignificant. Similar results were obtained in numerous other test cases. The conclusion is that major changes in Γ and thus sound speed are important. Minor considerations, such as where the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition takes place, details of how parameters are extrapolated, or detailed composition assumptions are relatively unimportant.

The final aspect of the phase space which must be explored is the role of composition gradients (*i.e.*, a nonzero A^*). The results indicate that composition gradients can play a significant role in oscillation frequencies. Compare, for example, cases B and C, BB and CC, FF2 and FF3, K and KK, L and LL, F and G, and finally P and R. In each calculation, the period of the 2f mode is longer in the nonzero A^* case, by an average of 2.4 min. The higher degree modes are less affected, though their periods tend to be a bit ($\lesssim 0.5$ min) shorter in the stably stratified case than in the neutrally stratified one. As is especially evident in the four K and L cases, this variation in the higher degree modes is larger than that produced by varying J_4 . However this higher degree period offset is at a level less than the second order theoretical uncertainty of 1% (Section 2.4), and is unlikely to be recognized in actual data. In contrast the lengthening of the 2f mode period is a bit over 1% and might be apparent.

It should also be noted that if such composition gradients are actually present in Saturn, gravity (or g) modes of the planet might also be excited. Such modes would arise from the resonant interaction of buoyancy dominated gravity waves. These g-modes produce much smaller density perturbations inside the planet than

the acoustic modes and would leave little trace of their presence outside the planet. The g-modes are thus virtually undetectable and are not further considered here.

Several conclusion can now be drawn from the calculations presented so far. Despite a relatively large phase space of uncertainty regarding Saturn and its interior, the low degree f-mode oscillation periods of the planet show surprisingly little variation. The 2f mode is most sensitive to assumptions about the interior, while the periods of the higher degree ($l \gtrsim 4$) modes vary by less than 1%, even when relatively severe corners of the phase space are investigated. Overall the mode periods are most sensitive to the assumed value of the gravitational harmonic J_4 (and hence core size), then the assumed presence or absence of composition gradients, and finally assumptions about the thermodynamic parameter Γ near the molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition. Under extreme assumptions, however, a highly perturbed Γ may significantly alter the lowest degree oscillation mode periods. Such circumstances, however, are probably highly unlikely.

4.4 Rotation Correction Calculation Considerations

The zero order oscillation periods of the previous section are of theoretical importance only. Actual oscillation periods of Saturn will be severely perturbed by the rotation of the planet. The theory of the first and second order rotation corrections, which produces the actual observed periods, was presented in Chapter 2 and the equations in Appendix I. These calculations depend upon oscillation frequencies and eigenmodes calculated in the previous section. As was the case in Section 4.2, however, there is an uncertainty phase space within which the rotation correction calculation must proceed.

The basics of the rotation corrections are actually straightforward. As can be seen from Appendix I, most of the correction terms involve integrals over the planetary density $\rho(r)$ and various derivatives of the oscillation eigenmodes. In these expansions eigenmodes of modes other than the one being considered are often required. Calculation of the rotation corrections for the 4f mode, for example, may require the oscillation eigenmodes and eigenfrequencies of the 2f, 3f, 4f, 5f, and 6f modes, depending on which assumptions about the planetary rotation are made. Results for the associated low overtone p-modes (*i.e.* the 4p1 – 4p3 modes) are also required. Thus in addition to the quantities presented in the previous section, the associated p-mode results were also found for many of the cases investigated. As stated in Appendix I, p-modes of radial degree $n \gtrsim 4$ while technically required for the calculations, were found to make no significant contribution to the rotation corrected oscillation frequencies.

As discussed in Section 2.3 and Appendix I, several new quantities describing the planetary interior model are required for the rotation correction. One, the ellipticity of level surfaces of the rotating Saturn, is supplied by the planetary inversion program. Others, such as derivatives of pressure, density, and gravitational potential are easily produced. The only new term which carries any significant uncertainty is K_s , the compression modulus defined in Equation 2.21. Since this is another term containing Γ , the Γ uncertainty phase space must again be explored in the rotation correction calculation.

The most significant question in the rotation correction, however, is how to treat the rotation of the planet itself. Does Saturn rotate as a solid body, or does it rotate differentially? Ingersoll and coworkers proposed that the interior of Saturn rotates differentially on cylinders and that the observed zonal wind profile

of the planet is the surface expression of these rotating cylinders (Smith *et al.* 1982; Ingersoll and Pollard 1982; Ingersoll and Miller 1986). One rationale behind this proposal is that it is very difficult to explain the zonal winds while restricting them to a thin outer shell of the planet. Other workers, however, have questioned this assumption (Allison and Stone 1983; Conrath and Gierasch 1984). Furthermore in a compressible, adiabatic fluid sphere, steady, finite-amplitude motions have cylindrical structure (Mestel 1965). Since the zonal jets on Saturn are steady finite-amplitude motions, the velocity structure would be expected to continue on concentric cylinders beneath the cloud tops into the deep interior, if the interior is adiabatic. Since at least some of the cases considered here assume complete adiabaticity, differential cylindrical rotation should be explored. Finally Kirk and Stevenson (1987) pointed out that hydromagnetic effects in the molecular hydrogen region must also be considered when discussing the deep rotation of the planet. They concluded that the “magnetic” interior must rotate at the magnetospheric rate, while some differential rotation in the outer portions of the planet would be expected. Uncertainty over the conductivity of H₂ precludes determination of the size of the uniformly rotating core, although the region would be larger than proposed by Ingersoll *et al.* . Determination of the correct $\Omega_P(r, \theta)$ is thus problematical.

Recall from Equation (2.19) the expansion of the planetary rotational frequency,

$$\Omega_P = \Omega_P(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \Omega_d(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \sum_{i=\text{even}}^k \Omega_{di}(r) Y_{i,0}(\theta, \varphi) \quad (4.20)$$

where θ is the colatitude. To keep the rotation correction manageable, $k = 2$ is used for modelling the differential rotation. To model differential rotation on cylinders,

Figure 4.8. Saturnian zonal wind velocities from Smith *et al.* (1982) normalized to the radio rotation frequency. The quantities shown here (diamonds) were produced by averaging the northern and southern hemisphere data to produce a latitudinally symmetric profile. The solid line is produced using Equation 4.21 with $f = 0.05$. The dashed line a best fit to all the data with $f = 0.03$.

Equation 4.20 is reduced to

$$\Omega_P = \Omega_P(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \Omega_d(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \left[1 + f \left(\frac{r}{R} \sin \theta \right)^2 \right]. \quad (4.21)$$

The parameter f fits the magnitude of the differential rotation. Figure 4.8 compares the zonal wind pattern of Saturn with two values of f . The best fit to the data is provided by $f = 0.032$ while a maximum value might be $f = 0.05$. Neither of

these fits, however, model the data particularly well. This may be because the point at which the zonal flow velocity is zero (near latitude $\pm 40^\circ$) may represent the size of the non-differentially rotating core (Kirk and Stevenson 1987). The treatment of Equation 4.21, however, assumes that the planet remains differentially rotating all the way to the core, as illustrated in Figure 4.9. If the Kirk and Stevenson model is correct, the radial rotation profile of the planet is probably closer to the lower dashed line in Figure 4.9 than the upper lines which arise from Equation 4.21. Application of the Kirk and Stevenson model, however, would necessitate at least 1 and possibly 2 more terms in the Fourier-like expansion of the rotation profile. These additional terms would significantly complicate the rotation correction calculation. Instead, the role of differential rotation will be studied in the next section by setting f equal to 0.0, 0.03, and 0.05. In this way the effect of possible differential rotation may at least be bounded.

4.5 Second Order Calculation Results

Calculations of the second order oscillation periods were made for only for a subset of the cases listed in Table 4.3. The cases chosen for more detailed consideration, A, K, L, J4P, J4M, and F, span the range of oscillation periods presented in Section 4.3. All of the important uncertainties identified in that section are represented here. Calculation results are presented in Table 4.6 for f-modes through degree $l = 8$. In this table, only the periods of orders $m = l$ are presented. For example, rather than list the 17 periods associated with the $l = 8$ f-mode (for orders $m = -8, \dots, 0, \dots, 8$), only the period of the $m = l = 8$ oscillation mode is listed. Other orders do not generally produce resonances with ring particle orbits

Figure 4.9. Models of Saturnian differential rotation with radius. The solid and long dashed lines arise from Equation 4.21 with f equal to 0.05 and 0.03. Note than in these cases the differential rotation persists all the way to the center. The short dashed line illustrates the approximate profile predicted by Kirk and Stevenson (1987).

(although a few special cases will be considered in the next chapter). Also the periods tabulated are those seen by an observer on the rotating planet. The frequency seen by an observer in inertial space may be obtained by converting a tabulated period into frequency and adding $m\Omega_0$. For each calculation the differential rotation parameter f is listed.

Table 4.6

Saturn f-mode Oscillation Periods (min)

Second Order; Mode $m = l$

mode	A			F			K			L		
	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$
2f	424.4	419.7	417.1	259.4	257.6	256.6	263.2	261.5	260.3	265.6	263.8	262.6
3f	205.9	203.9	202.8	184.7	182.6	181.5	184.1	182.3	181.0	184.1	182.0	180.8
4f	161.3	159.2	158.1	151.5	149.3	148.0	150.2	148.2	146.9	150.2	148.0	146.6
5f	136.6	134.5	133.1	131.7	129.2	127.7	130.4	128.3	126.9	130.6	128.2	126.8
6f	120.3	118.2	116.8	117.8	115.5	114.0	117.1	114.8	113.4	117.1	114.8	113.4
7f	109.4	106.9	105.5	107.8	105.4	103.8	107.3	104.9	103.4	107.2	104.9	103.4
8f	101.1			99.91	97.45	95.87	99.60	97.17	95.62	99.59	97.16	95.61

mode	J4P			J4M			KK		
	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$
2f	253.3	251.7	250.7	268.2	266.5	265.2	268.2	266.5	265.2
3f	181.5	179.7	178.5	188.0	186.0	184.7	188.0	186.0	184.7
4f	149.9	147.7	146.4	152.8	150.7	149.3	152.8	150.7	149.3
5f	130.9	128.5	127.1	132.1	129.9	128.4	132.1	129.9	128.4
6f	117.5	115.2	113.7	118.1	115.8	114.3	118.1	115.8	114.3
7f	107.7	105.3	103.7	107.9	105.5	104.0	107.9	105.5	104.0
8f	100.0	97.52	95.94	99.93	97.47	95.91	99.93	97.47	95.91

There are no major surprises among the data in Table 4.6. In cases where the zero order periods differed little, such as the higher degree modes of cases K and L, the second order results also show little variation. The Γ uncertainty evaluated in these two cases produces no larger variation in second order than it does in first. The same is true for variation between the PRF and 273 models. Comparing cases F and K reveals that the period difference between models persists in second order at the same magnitude, typically less than 1 min, although the differences are slightly magnified. Case A, which presents the worst case Γ variation continues to be the most different from the other models for very low degree modes. By $l = 4$, however, the periods remain consistent with the other calculations. Finally the two cases J4P and J4M continue to show generally the widest variation in periods (excluding case A). As in the 273/PRF model comparisons, the period difference in second order between the two models does increase by a percent or two. Thus while not drastically changing the relationships among models, the $m = l$ oscillation periods do slightly magnify their differences.

The most interesting results from the second order calculation are the variations in period with f , the differential rotation parameter. As f is increased from 0.0 to 0.03 to 0.05, the $m = l$ oscillation periods decrease relative to the solid body rotation case. This is due to the differential rotation induced increase in rotation rate with distance from the rotation axis. Those modes travelling in the direction of rotation ($m > 0$) are accelerated in the direction of motion, lowering the oscillation period (Vorontsov 1981). Furthermore the higher degree modes exhibit a much larger perturbation. This is explained by the lower depth of propagation of these modes; they experience the more rapid rotation of the outer layers and not the deeper, slower rotation (Vorontsov 1981). This trend implies that if the shallow

differential rotation model of Kirk and Stevenson (1987) is correct, then the low degree modes will be only slightly perturbed from their solid body rotation periods while the higher degree modes will experience a perturbation close to what has been calculated here. Therefore the range of periods predicted by the simple differential rotation model used here should encompass that which would be produced by the Kirk and Stevenson model.

This behavior of the mode periods may be useful for diagnosing the interior state of the planet from period observations. The low degree modes are strongly affected by interior model differences (witness the J4P/J4M cases) and less by differential rotation. For the higher degree modes, by comparison, the differential rotation signal is larger than the interior model one. This is because the outer layers of most all of the Saturn models are very similar, minimizing inter-model period differences. For the reasons explained above, these same modes are those most strongly affected by differential rotation. These trends are illustrated in Figure 4.10 which plots the percentage change in oscillation period with degree produced by differential rotation and core size.

At this point it is important to recall the estimate from Section 2.4 of the theoretical uncertainty of this second order period calculation. This uncertainty was estimated as $\sim 1\%$. Hence inter-model differences greater than this value are significant and could prove useful in inversion attempts using real data. The effects of differential rotation and core size clearly exceed 1%. Questions about the interior sound speed and treatment of Γ , as exemplified in cases K and L, produce inter-case differences of less than this amount. The contribution of compositional layering is right at 1%. These differences are also indicated on Figure 4.10. This is an especially useful result. It means that if the periods of these low degree f-modes

Figure 4.10. Sensitivity of the f-mode oscillation frequency to changes in model assumptions with varying oscillation degree l . Differences are measured from the most similar case with only the one trait varying. The horizontal long dashed line represents the estimated 1% theoretical uncertainty.

can be detected, then they will contain useful, new information about the interior state of Saturn. Questions regarding the size of the rock/ice core and the rotation state of the planet can be addressed. Other questions, which would normally complicate interpretation of this data, such as the high pressure behavior of Γ , are of secondary importance. Complexities introduced by unknowns such as compositional layering or extreme Γ variation, as attested to by case A, cannot be totally dismissed however.

Table 4.7

Saturnian f-mode Oscillation Periods (min)
Second Order; Mode $m = l$

mode	V ¹	mean	All ² std. dev.	%
2f	287	261.4	4.93	1.9
3f	201	184.5	1.90	1.0
4f	163	151.0	1.00	0.66
5f	140	131.2	0.60	0.46
6f	126	117.6	0.38	0.33
7f	113	107.6	0.28	0.26
8f	105	99.84	0.18	0.18

¹ Vorontsov (1981); ² From Table 4.6, $f = 0$, excluding A.

Finally these results should be compared with those of Vorontsov (1981) which are shown for the same 8 modes in Table 4.7. Although the agreement with the zero order periods in Table 4.5 was good, the rotation corrected periods agree less well. The periods calculated from this work are generally shorter than those of Vorontsov, sometimes by as much as 10%. The same rotation correction program applied to Jupiter models, however, produced excellent period agreements with Vorontsov. The source of this disparity could not be identified. The observation that differences between models are magnified by the rotation correction would account for some portion of the difference, however.

4.6 Summary

In this chapter I have presented the techniques and considerations necessary to calculate the oscillation periods of Saturn. First zeroth order periods, appropriate to a non-rotating planet, were found. Principal sources of model and thermodynamic uncertainties were evaluated. Most uncertain parameters had little effect

over calculated oscillation periods. The most important model parameters which affected the results were core size and compositional layering. The second order corrections to these periods were then found, using the theory of Vorontsov (1981). The principal uncertainty arising in the rotation correction is the rotation state of the planet itself. If Saturn rotates differentially on cylinders, the periods of some f-mode oscillations may be modified by up to 2 - 3%. The lower ($l \sim 2 - 4$) degree modes are more sensitive to the deep planetary interior while the higher degree modes provide more information about differential rotation. Detection of actual Saturnian oscillation periods could thus provide important new constraints on these aspects of Saturn's interior.

CHAPTER 5

RING SEISMOLOGY

Using the data from the previous chapters, this chapter addresses the central issue of this thesis, “Are Saturn’s rings a seismograph?”. Comparisons between predicted resonance locations and the ring data indicate that some C-ring features may in fact be produced by planetary oscillation modes. The evidence for this conclusion is presented and suggestions for future observations are made. The implied oscillation amplitudes are also computed. All of the results are found to provide consistent, but not conclusive, evidence for the hypothesis.

5.1 Preliminary Considerations

The oscillation periods calculated in the previous section may now be used to determine the radial location in the rings where resonances are expected to be found. For conceptual purposes it is useful to recall Equation 3.15 which gives the approximate relation between orbital and pattern frequencies at an outer resonance:

$$\frac{\Omega(r_{L,V})}{\Omega_p} \approx \frac{m}{m+1}. \quad (5.1)$$

The pattern frequency for a given mode may be found from the oscillation periods reported in Table 4.6 by converting to frequency and adding $m\Omega_0$. Then by using (5.1), or more accurately (3.12) or (3.13) with the appropriate sign, the orbital frequency of the ring particles at resonance may be found. Finally by iteratively solving Equation 3.14, the radius of the resonance r_L or r_V is determined.

To estimate the uncertainty of the radius estimate, note that $\Omega(r_{L,V}) \propto \Omega_p$ and that, to zeroth order, $r_{L,V} \propto \Omega^{-2/3}$. Hence $r_{L,V} \propto \Omega_p^{-2/3}$. The percent

uncertainty in $r_{L,V}$ is then given by $\frac{2}{3} \times 1\%$ (Bevington 1969), where the 1% error estimate in oscillation periods was derived in Section 2.4. For the region of the C-ring under consideration here, this amounts to a error in location of the resonance of about ± 550 km. The situation for oscillation resonances is thus quite different from that of satellite resonances. Because the orbital elements of satellites are usually known with high accuracy, predicted ring resonances are often fixed within 5 km or less. The large error bars on the oscillation resonance locations imply that ring seismology must be conducted from a different perspective than is the case with satellite resonances. A single correspondence between a predicted oscillation resonance location and a ring feature is insufficient evidence of the resonance. Numerous, consistent overlaps will be required for the hypothesis to be convincing.

5.2 Outer Lindblad and Vertical Resonances

Table 5.1 lists the Outer Lindblad Resonances (OLRs) for each of the oscillation mode periods listed in Table 4.6. The resonance locations have been computed using Equation 3.12 with the positive coefficient of κ , and setting $m = l$. Thus the computed resonances range from the 2:3 OLR of the order $m = 2$ 2f-mode up through the 8:9 OLR of the $m = 8$ 8f-mode. For each case resonances were computed for differential rotation coefficients $f = 0.0, 0.03, \text{ and } 0.05$. The central values of the gravitational harmonics from Table 1.1 were used in computing orbital frequencies in all cases. Varying the harmonics across their error bars moved resonance locations by at most a few kilometers.

Several generalities may be ascertained directly from Table 5.1. The 2f oscillation mode produces the resonance furthest from the planet. This is because the 2f mode has the longest oscillation period and the coefficient in Equation 5.1 is

Table 5.1

Saturn f-mode Outer Lindblad Oscillation Resonances (km)
Order $m = l$

mode	A		F		K		L					
	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$									
2f	101269	100944	100762	86233	86008	85882	86693	86484	86345	86974	86762	86621
3f	84865	84579	84420	81713	81394	81216	81625	81333	81140	81626	81286	81093
4f	82521	82175	81983	80806	80402	80177	80573	80204	79961	80580	80158	79915
5f	81856	81418	81175	80885	80378	80084	80637	80200	79912	80671	80178	79891
6f	81774	81313	81026	81240	80733	80399	81084	80585	80258	81081	80584	80257
7f	82158	81573	81249	81778	81218	80851	81663	81111	80748	81657	81105	80742
8f	82648			82353	81746	81348	82277	81677	81283	82274	81674	81280

mode	J4P		J4M		KK		
	$f = 0$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0.03$	$f = 0.05$	$f = 0$	
2f	85479	85280	85148	87305	87080	86930	86115
3f	81207	80918	80728	82258	81923	81719	81682
4f	80520	80112	79897	81087	80660	80407	80758
5f	80732	80240	79948	80968	80520	80225	80831
6f	81164	80658	80325	81303	80797	80464	81252
7f	81760	81198	80829	81805	81247	80881	81798
8f	82375	81765	81365	82358	81754	81358	82381

closer to unity for all other modes. For a given pattern frequency, the smaller the coefficient, the larger the resonance radii. As oscillation degree increases, however, the analysis becomes slightly more complex. The oscillation order m is embedded in both the rotation correction and the pattern frequency. As l and m increase from 2 to 8, resonance locations first move inward from about 86600 km to about 80000 km and then move outward again, to about 82000 km by degree $l = 8$. Simply by examining the zeroth order oscillation periods in Table 4.5, one might not expect this result.

The variation in resonance radii produced by varying J_4 and the differential rotation parameter f is more easily understood. For a given oscillation resonance, increasing the oscillation period moves the resonance outward. As f is increased, the $m = l$ oscillation mode periods decrease, and the resonance locations move towards the planet. For the 2f modes, the differential rotation induced change in location is about 350 km and for the 8f modes the change is about 1000 km. Following from Chapter 4, increasing the core size by changing from case J4P to case J4M moves the 2f mode resonance outwards by almost 2000 km. So, as previously established, the uncertainty in f easily produces the largest variation in the high degree f-mode resonance locations. For the lower degree modes, other sources of error produce larger differences.

A graphical presentation of the information in Table 5.1 is contained in Figures 5.1 through 5.4. The black bars indicate the variation in resonance location due to the stated model uncertainty. For example, in Figure 5.1 as J_4 is allowed to vary across its error bar, the location of the 2:1 OLR for the 2f mode varies from 85480 km (for J4P) to 87305 km (for J4M). The error bars protruding from each side illustrate the additional 550 km theoretical uncertainty discussed in the previous

Figure 5.1. Location of Outer Lindblad Resonances for sectoral mode oscillations of varying degree l . Left side of black bar locates position of resonance for case J4P, right side J4M. Error bars indicate theoretical uncertainty of ~ 550 km. Upward pointing arrows locate position of unassociated OLR/IVR type waves (see Table 3.2) identified by Rosen (1989). Hatched region represents the Maxwell gap.

section. These error bars are not shown on every figure. The upward pointing arrows along the bottom of the page locate the position of the 6 unassociated OLR/IVR type waves identified by Rosen (1989) and listed in Table 3.2. The hatched region near 87500 km marks the Maxwell gap. The radial distance covered

Figure 5.2. Same as Figure 4.1, except bars indicate variation of differential rotation parameter f . Right side of bar represents $f = 0$, left side $f = 0.05$. Variation shown for case F.

in Figures 5.3 and 5.4 is slightly different from that in Figures 5.1 and 5.2. To provide scale, the radial limits in Figure 5.4 correspond to the inner and outer edges of the C-ring.

The first result seen in Figures 5.1 and 5.2 is that the planetary oscillation mode resonances span the same radial region of the central C-ring (~ 80000 to 88000 km) where the unexplained OLR/IVR type waves are located. Not surprisingly, given

Figure 5.3. Same as Figure 4.1, except largest excursion in resonance radii from Table 5.1 (excluding case A) are shown. Open squares indicate resonance locations for the same modes using the second order oscillation frequencies of Vorontsov (1981).

the uncertainty in resonance locations, most of the predicted resonances overlap a ring feature. However, further inspection indicates that there is no obvious pattern of correlations. Also the high degree modes which produce many resonances near 81500 km do not seem to be producing waves. If there are indeed correlations, they would seem to be only for the lower degree modes.

Table 5.2

Possible OLR Ring Associations†

Mode	Location (km)	Feature	m_{obs}	m_{OLR}	Consistent?
2f	87400	Maxwell gap	—	2	yes
	85465	OLR/IVR	1–2	2	yes
	84650	OLR/IVR	2–5	2	yes
3f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	3	yes
	82065	OLR/IVR	2–4	3	yes
	82211	OLR/IVR	2–5	3	yes
4f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	4	yes
5f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	5	yes
6f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	6	yes
7f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	7	yes
	82065	OLR/IVR	2–4	7	no
	82211	OLR/IVR	2–5	7	no
8f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	8	yes
	82065	OLR/IVR	2–4	8	no
	82211	OLR/IVR	2–5	8	no

†Wave data from Rosen (1989).

To further consider resonance locations, Figure 5.3 was prepared. For each oscillation degree the resonances farthest from and closest to the planet were found from Table 5.1, neglecting case A. For example, for the 2f mode the farthest resonance is produced by the case J4M, $f = 0$; the closest resonance is from case J4P, $f = 0.05$. The theoretical error bars are also shown. This figure thus indicates the widest reasonable variation to be expected in predicted resonance location. In addition the open squares indicate the resonances predicted from the frequencies given by Vorontsov (1981). As reported in the last Chapter, those frequencies are generally lower, producing resonances slightly farther out than those found here. The Vorontsov locations do no better at predicting ring feature locations.

Individual correspondences may be examined more easily using Figure 5.3. The 2f mode bar overlaps the location of three unassociated features: the Maxwell gap and two OLR/IVR type waves. The 3f mode overlaps three wave features. Oscillation modes 4f, 5f, and 6f all overlap the same feature, while modes 7f and 8f each overlap three. Table 5.2 lists these correspondences, the wave properties from Table 3.2, and whether or not the predicted m value agrees with Rosen's (1989) observational constraint. Clearly, however, not all these correspondences could be true. Each mode can produce one wave feature and each feature could only be produced by one oscillation mode. An internally consistent subset of the correspondences from Table 5.2 is listed in Table 5.3. In this case the Maxwell gap, located on the right side of the 2f mode error bar, is attributed to this oscillation. The wave at 82211 km is paired with the 3f mode 3:4 OLR and the wave at 82065 km with the 4f mode 4:5 OLR. The first wave lies at the right outside of the 3f mode error bar while the second wave just misses the right side of the 4f bar. Finally the wave at 80990 km, lying at the right of the 5f bar, is assigned this mode. No other OLR/IVR type waves are assigned an oscillation mode. The higher degree modes are presumed not to produce sufficient torque to launch a wave. This set of attributions, while just one of several that could be made, makes the largest number of internally consistent pairings and will be used for further discussion purposes. For these pairings the m constraint of Rosen (1989) is met for each wave. Also each location is chosen from a consistent region of each error bar, namely the large radius side. Since the radii predicted from a given case tend to stay in the same relative location of each mode's error bar, consistently choosing from the same error bar region is roughly equivalent to using the same planetary model. An exception to this rule of thumb would be in the case of the Kirk and Stevenson (1987) differential rotation law. In this case low degree mode resonances

Table 5.3

Possible OLR Ring Associations†
(One Consistent Set)

Mode	Location (km)	Feature	m_{obs}	m_{OLR}	Consistent?
2f	87400	Maxwell gap	—	2	yes
3f	82211	OLR/IVR	2–5	3	yes
4f	82065	OLR/IVR	2–4	4	yes‡
5f	80990	OLR/IVR	3–11	5	yes

†Wave data from Rosen (1989). ‡Lies outside 4f 4:5 OLR error bar range.

would lie to the right hand side of the bar in Figure 5.2, resonances with higher degree modes, which are more influenced by the shallow differential rotation, would lie to the left.

To test the assertion in Section 3.4 that few Outer Vertical Resonances of oscillation modes fall in the C-ring, periods of the order $m = l - 1$ modes were calculated for the two extreme models J4P ($f = 0.05$) and J4M ($f = 0.0$). Locations of OVRs were then determined for each mode (these are vertical resonances since $l + m = l + (l - 1)$ is odd). As shown in Figure 5.4, only a few high degree modes produce OVRs in the C-ring. The degree of uncertainty is comparable to the OLRs from order $m = l$ modes. There are clearly no wave overlaps for modes of degree $l > 5$, the same conclusion reached for the Lindblad resonances. Apparently these modes are not excited to sufficient amplitude to launch waves in the rings. The $l = 5$, $m = 4$ mode does, however, overlap with the wave at 74945 km (Table 5.4). This wave propagates in the direction opposite to most of the other C-ring waves and is assumed by Rosen (1989) to be launched at either an OVR or an ILR (this wave variety is indicated by the downward pointing arrows in the figure). Thus the resonance type (OVR or ILR) is consistent with the model prediction (OVR).

Figure 5.4. Similar to Figure 5.3. Radius scale varies from inner to outer C-ring edges. Downward pointing arrows indicate unassociated OVR/ILR type waves (see Table 3.2) identified by Rosen (1989). Small solid squares and triangles indicate respectively location of OLR and OVR resonances predicted by case A. Solid bars on the left represent maximum variation in OVR locations for modes $m = l - 1$ (excluding case A). Location of case A $l = 2$ OLR lies in B-ring.

Rosen, however, listed this feature as having 2 to 3 spiral arms; we predict 4. Since this wave is the weakest unassociated wave which could be identified in the C-ring (Rosen 1989), the m assignment may be less accurate.

Table 5.4

Possible OVR Ring Association†

Mode	Location (km)	Feature	m_{obs}	m_{OVR}	Consistent?
5f	74945	OVR/ILR	2-3	4	no‡

†Wave data from Rosen (1989). ‡ m off by one.**Table 5.5**

C-Ring Features Still Unassociated†

Location (km)	Feature	m_{obs}
83638	OLR/IVR	3-8
84656	OLR/IVR	2-5
85465	OLR/IVR	1-2
85690	OVR/ILR	1-3

†Wave data from Rosen (1989).

Beyond these five tentative wave associations, no other correlations between oscillation modes and ring features can be made. Of the eight similar unexplained wave features in the C-ring found by Rosen (1989), four are still unassociated. These waves are listed in Table 5.5. These waves are disconcertingly similar to those attributed to oscillation modes in Table 5.3 in morphology, amplitude, and location, yet they cannot be associated with any resonances. This failure to produce resonances with either all or none of the currently unexplained C-ring features makes interpretation of the results somewhat more difficult. It cannot be said that there is no evidence of oscillation produced waves, which would be the case if there were no resonances. And it cannot be said that the correlation is very strong, as would be the case if all the features were explained. Until further wave observations, discussed in Section 5.4 are made, this ambiguity cannot be removed.

Finally, the largest variation in resonance location has yet to be discussed. Case A, in which a large period variation was induced by severely perturbing the thermodynamic parameter Γ , produces very different OLR and OVR locations from those discussed above. These locations are shown in Figure 5.4 by the solid squares (for OLRs) and triangles (for OVRs). The case A resonances are not meant to be associated with a particular model, but rather to indicate the extent to which positions might be disturbed by an extreme variation in the thermodynamic parameters of the planetary interior. The higher degree results are little changed from the other cases and locations of the higher degree mode resonances overlap no better with the observed ring features. The lower degree modes show more variation. The $2f$ mode OLR falls in a complex region of the B ring. Of more interest is the $l = 2$, $m = 1$ OVR. This feature may place a limit on the degree to which Γ might be perturbed, assuming the $2f$ mode is excited sufficiently to produce any ring feature. Note that there is no OVR wave with an m range which encompasses unity inside of 85500 km. Thus Γ is either much less perturbed than in model A, in which case this resonance would lie inside of inner C-ring edge, or even more perturbed to produce a resonance at the OVR/ILR wave at 85690 km. If the latter scenario were true, it is possible that, combined with significant differential rotation, more correlations with ring features might be found. This particular wave feature is the second largest in the C-ring and is especially difficult to explain as a satellite produced density wave and cannot be a satellite produced bending wave (Rosen 1989). As such it would be especially useful to associate this wave with a planetary OVR. Fine-tuning an extreme model variation to explain this particular wave, however, seems uncalled for. The more likely explanation is that such extreme model variations do not exist.

5.3 Second Order and Corotation Resonances

As discussed in Chapter 3, there are resonance types other than the vertical and Lindblad resonances investigated above. Corotation resonances arise when the pattern frequency of the gravitational perturbation is equal to the orbital frequency of the ring particles. In this case the perturbation potential is stationary in the frame of the ring particles. Resulting azimuthal accelerations may produce the appearance of an m lobed azimuthal structure (Lin *et al.* 1987). The single-cut radio science occultation data, however, are not particularly well suited to the task of searching for such azimuthal variation. Second order vertical and horizontal resonances, in contrast, may produce wave and gap features like their first order cousins. But since the forcing is not at the vertical or epicyclic frequencies of the ring particles, but rather at a harmonic, the torque is substantially reduced. Thus if first order resonances are just marginally capable of producing ring features, second order resonances are unlikely to be seen in the radio data.

Corotation features, as predicted, are difficult to identify in the data. The only investigated oscillation modes with sufficiently low pattern frequencies to produce corotation resonances in the C-ring are the $7f$ and $8f$ modes. For the J4M case ($f = 0$) these resonances lie at 74584 and 75874 km respectively. Since this is the long period calculation, other cases will produce resonances inside of these limits. These radii fall just at the inside edge of the C-ring. At both locations there is in fact some structure, unlike most other, relatively bland, regions of the C-ring. These low amplitude features are not waves, extend over radii of about 150 to 250 km, and are unlikely to be produced by a single resonance. In any event, lack of azimuthal coverage makes interpretation virtually impossible. Available C-ring

imaging data should be examined, however, to determine if there is azimuthal variation in these features.

The presence of any second order features is tested more easily. Using the same model, second order Outer Horizontal Resonances (OHR) (the second order version of Lindblad resonances) all lie outwards of 88250 km. The $l = m = 2$ and $l = m = 3$ mode oscillations second order OHR both lie in the thick B-ring, where the radio data is too noisy to search for features. The $l = m = 4$ resonance lies in a bland area of the outer C-ring near 91370 km. Unlike the first order OLR cases, there are no promising unexplained ring features within 1000 km of this resonance. The other resonances, all lying outwards of 88000 km, are similarly placed. The conclusion is that second order resonances are not an important planetary oscillation mode phenomenon, at least in the C-ring.

5.4 Oscillation Amplitude Requirements

The oscillation resonance location data from Section 5.2 seemed to provide at least circumstantial evidence that resonances with planetary oscillation modes were responsible for several C-ring features. This section examines the energetics implied by the putative associations. By using the equation for the torque produced at a resonance (3.17), the values of m found above, the empirical wave feature torque requirements of Rosen (1989 and Section 3.4), and the oscillation eigenfunctions calculated in Chapter 4, it is now possible to determine the mode amplitudes required to produce the particular gap and waves in the rings.

Using oscillation eigenfunctions from case CC, the oscillation mode amplitudes (at $r = R$) necessary to open a gap or launch a wave at the resonance locations found above were computed. Results are shown in Table 5.6. For a typical mode,

Table 5.6

Minimum Oscillation Mode Amplitudes¹
Required To Produce Ring Features

mode	Feature	
	wave	gap
2f	0.02 m	0.6 m
3f	0.03	0.9
4f	0.05	1.5
5f	0.08	2.3
6f	0.12	3.6
7f	0.19	5.5
8f	0.29	8.4

¹at $r = R$.

planetary oscillation amplitudes of ~ 2 m are required for gap opening; wave amplitudes of ~ 10 cm are required for density wave production. Note that as degree increases, the required amplitudes also increase because less mass is oscillating. The result for wave launching is remarkable. If waves with a surface amplitude of only 10 centimeters are present on Saturn, they should produce a detectable signature in the rings. This amplitude corresponds to a wave velocity of $\sim 10^{-3}$ cm s⁻¹. This number is large compared to the amplitudes predicted by Goldreich and Kumar for the standard Saturn convection case, but slightly smaller than the amplitudes predicted for a vigorously convecting Saturn. Dolginov and Muslimov (1984) predicted mode velocities $\lesssim 10^{-2}$ cm s⁻¹. Thus amplitudes necessary to apply sufficient torque for density wave production seem to be at least marginally energetically feasible on Saturn. The gap opening amplitude is more problematical, but does occur for the longest period mode, which would couple most efficiently to convection. These calculations are also the source of the mode energies reported

Figure 5.5. Various important torques T^L/Σ applied by Lindblad resonances on the C-ring (Σ is the local surface mass density). The Atlas 2:1 ILR launches no wave visible in the radio science data, the Mimas 4:1 ILR produces an obvious density wave, and the Mimas 3:1 and Pandora 2:1 ILRs apply torques slightly larger and smaller than the line labeled 'gap' and both are apparently associated with C-ring gaps (Rosen 1989). The lines with symbols represent the OLR torques applied by sectoral modes through degree $l = 8$, assuming the indicated torque for the $l = 2$ model. See text for explanation of each case.

in Chapter 2. The energy in a 1 meter amplitude mode is about 5×10^{26} ergs. The energy in a 1 centimeter amplitude oscillation is about 5×10^{22} ergs.

By estimating the energy contained in a particular mode, the oscillation amplitude and hence the torque applied at resonance may be found. This procedure is

applied in Figure 5.5 where the torque applied by an $m = l$ OLR is plotted for each oscillation mode. To estimate the amplitude of each mode it is first assumed that the 2f 2:3 OLR is responsible for opening the Maxwell gap. This mode must then apply at least the minimum gap opening torque found by Rosen (1989 and Section 3.4) and indicated by the upper dashed line. Torques applied by subsequent modes are found by making one of two assumptions. The first possibility, illustrated by the solid line, is that each mode has the same energy E as in the 2f mode. This would be the case if the oscillations are in the efficient convective excitation region where $\sigma\tau_h \lesssim 1$ (using the Goldreich and Kumar (1987) convective excitation theory presented in Section 2.5). If instead convective excitation is inefficient ($\sigma\tau_h \gtrsim 1$), then $E \propto \sigma^{-13/2}$. The latter case is illustrated by the long dashed lines. Notice that the torque falls off much more rapidly in this case.

Also plotted in Figure 5.5 is the torque applied at the Mimas 4:1 resonance which is sufficient to launch a wave. The weaker Atlas 2:1 resonance, indicated by the bottom dashed line, does not produce a wave detectable in the radio science data. The minimum torque to launch a wave thus falls between the Mimas and Atlas lines. Similarly the gap opening torque falls between the upper two dashed lines. Comparing these limits with the two different energy assumptions produces a striking result. If all modes have the energy in the supposed gap opening 2f mode, the torque falls very little between resonances. Thus many gaps and waves would be expected to be seen if one is seen. On the other hand, if the energy falls off more rapidly, only a handful of features should be expected if the 2f mode has a large amplitude. In this case one gap and three or four wave features would be close to what is expected. This is in fact what is seen in the data. The 2f mode might be producing the Maxwell gap, the 3f and 4f modes may be associated with relatively

large amplitude waves (1.3 and 1.6 $\delta\tau/\tau$ respectively), and the 5f mode is paired with a small amplitude wave ($\delta\tau/\tau \sim 0.7$). Finally the putative $l = 5, m = 4$ OVR at 74945 km is the weakest wave feature identified in the ring. No waves from higher order modes are seen.

The energetics of the proposed oscillation modes are thus also consistent with the proposed C-ring wave associations. The number of ring features, the mode amplitudes required to excite them, the variation in effect on the rings with oscillation degree, and the possible forcing mechanisms are all, qualitatively at least, internally consistent. These consistencies combined with the location and wave characteristic arguments from the previous section, seem to strongly suggest that the C-ring features are in fact produced by resonances with planetary oscillation modes. But while consistent, the available data is not compelling. The next section examines what additional tests can be applied to these wave features to determine if they are indeed traces on the ring seismograph.

5.5 Observational Tests

While the agreement between the predicted oscillation resonances characteristics and observations is good, it does not constitute a definite detection of Saturnian f-mode oscillations. The oscillation resonance theory does, however, make some very specific, testable predictions about the character of the associated waves. First, the wave features listed in Table 5.3 should be density, not bending waves, since the theory predicts that they are excited at Outer Lindblad, not Vertical, resonances. The wave at 79495 km should be a bending wave not a density wave. Secondly the waves should have the specified number of spiral arms m_{OLR} or m_{OVR} . While the current predictions are generally consistent with the available

data, the ranges are still relatively large. Finally, of course, the theory predicts that no newly discovered satellites will have a resonance at those particular places in the C-ring. But how will these assumptions actually be tested?

The principal new source of data about Saturn's rings for the next decade or so will be Earth based observations of ring occultations. Stellar occultations of Saturn's rings may rarely be observed directly from the Earth. One such stellar occultation was observed at numerous sites around the planet during July 1989. Atmospheric seeing and the size of the star will limit the resolution in the ring plane of Saturn to about 10 km for this event. While the data are not yet reduced, it is unlikely that the C-ring waves will be resolved. Future occultations observed from the ground are unlikely to be much better. More promising would be occultations observed by Space Telescope, especially of small ultraviolet stars. The fundamental limit on ring plane resolution from an occultation is the Fresnel scale, $\lambda_F \approx \sqrt{\lambda D}$. At $\lambda = 0.2 \mu\text{m}$ and $D = 9.0 \text{ AU}$, a ring plane resolution of 500 m might be obtained. Since 200 meter resolution will likely be required to detail the C-ring waves, Earth centered occultation detection may only marginally provide new information.

More promising is the Cassini mission to Saturn. The Cassini spacecraft will go into orbit about Saturn in roughly the year 2000. During its mission it will observe occultations of stars passing behind the rings, and produce numerous radio occultations. These Cassini observations should be able to definitively determine if the proposed correspondences with ring features are in fact correct. The numerous stellar and radio occultation experiments conducted by the spacecraft will produce radial profiles of the rings at many different azimuths. This extensive azimuthal coverage of the rings should make determination of the number of spiral

arms in a given wave straightforward. Furthermore occultations conducted at different incidence angles to the rings should help resolve the bending wave/density wave question. Since the amount of material intercepting an occultation signal will vary with incidence angle for a bending wave but not a density wave, careful analysis of the same waves seen in several occultations should determine the wave nature. Also images of the waves and the Maxwell gap can also help place limits on their azimuthal structure. Finally Cassini will conduct a thorough search for any moonlets not found by the Voyager spacecraft. The most definite death knell for the oscillation resonance theory would be the discovery of new satellites capable of producing the observed waves.

If the waves as observed by Cassini do meet the tests set out here, then the oscillation-produced nature of the waves will be established. It is highly unlikely that any satellite not found by Cassini could produce the appropriate wave type with the correct number of spiral arms in the correct locations. The Cassini occultation observations should be conducted in such a way that the inner C-ring is well covered by the experiments.

There is one other potential new test which may be applied to this hypothesis. In this chapter only those resonances falling inside the C-ring were discussed. There is also material inside the C-ring, namely the D-ring. If there are in fact oscillation produced waves in the C-ring, the vertical resonances associated with each mode should produce waves in the D-ring. This ring is too thin to have produced a signal in the radio data. There are, however, long exposure images of this region. These images should be examined to see if any features are visible. If there are apparent wave features, there locations may be applied with those predicted by the theory.

Finally, a means of detecting similar oscillations of Jupiter has been suggested by Gautier (1987, personal communication) who has proposed placing a dedicated gravity spacecraft in close orbit around Jupiter. Such a spacecraft would search for Jovian f-mode oscillations. Careful monitoring of the acceleration of the spacecraft might identify gravitational perturbations produced by oscillation modes. The spacecraft itself would take the place of the ring particles at Saturn. As the analysis in Section 2.5 demonstrated, the more violent convection in Jupiter's atmosphere would most likely excite larger amplitude oscillations than at Saturn. Nevertheless, detecting them would be no easy feat. Numerous non-gravitational forces, especially those due to the plasma and magnetic environment around Jupiter, would make detecting slight gravitational accelerations very difficult. Furthermore the amplification of the gravitational signal by the orbital resonance phenomenon in the rings would not be available to the spacecraft. If detected, however, the analysis of the frequencies would be quite similar to that presented here.

5.6 Summary

In this chapter I have presented several lines of self consistent evidence that Saturn's rings are behaving as a seismograph, recording the presence of interior oscillation modes of the planet. Oscillation frequencies produced by current Saturn interior models predict resonances near five, apparently resonance produced, C-ring features and these features appear to be of types consistent with the proposed forcing in propagation direction and number of spiral arms (m). The variation of feature magnitude with oscillation degree l is consistent with that expected from oscillation excitation theory and the absolute oscillation amplitudes may be

obtainable. But because of large error bars on predicted oscillation frequencies, uncertainties regarding the detailed nature of the putative associated C-ring features, failure to find associations for several similar wave features, and questions regarding the excitation of the oscillation modes, the evidence falls short of compelling.

Fortunately the ring seismology hypothesis makes numerous specific predictions that future spacecraft missions to the planet should be able to test. Regardless of the outcome of these future experiments, which may lie more than a decade away, new and useful information about the deep interior of Saturn will be obtained. If the seismology hypothesis is found to be incorrect, stringent limits on the magnitude of the low degree f-mode oscillations of Saturn will be placed. Since low degree oscillation modes with amplitudes larger than about 10 cm should produce observable waves in the C-ring, failure to detect these waves produces a tight constraint on the Saturnian f-mode amplitudes. Combined with improved theories of acoustic mode excitation by turbulence, unique limits on deep atmospheric convective velocities on Saturn could be placed. Also planetary oscillations modes may be disregarded as a source of external gravitational field perturbations.

If instead the ring features listed in Tables 5.3 and 5.4 (or some other subset from Table 5.2) are found to be consistent with the proposed forcing mechanism, then significant new information about the interior structure of Saturn may be gleaned. Using the proposed associations, it could be concluded that there is no deep differential rotation on Saturn (consistent with Kirk and Stevenson 1988), the core size is slightly larger than the standard model would predict, and there are no large regions of depressed sound speed (due to an extended transition region from molecular to metallic hydrogen). Slight composition gradients cannot be ruled out

however. If a single consistent set of ring features is indeed found, more extensive investigations into Saturnian oscillation behavior will be warranted.

CHAPTER 6

SUMMARY

This dissertation has investigated a new technique for detecting the nonradial oscillations of Saturn. The procedure is to use the rings as a seismograph to search for perturbations in the external gravitational field produced by Saturnian f-mode oscillations. The rings make an excellent seismograph since they are sensitive to slight gravitational perturbations and they fill a large volume of orbital frequency space. The modes themselves are detectable because they have long periods and potentially may produce large external gravitational perturbations. In the course of testing this concept, this work has provided the first look at the sensitivity of the f-mode oscillation frequencies to variations in interior models and thermodynamic parameters. Comparisons between the resultant predicted resonance locations and mode amplitudes with observed C-ring features provides compelling circumstantial, but not conclusive, evidence that the rings are recording planetary oscillations. The major results of this study are thus: 1) the rings make an excellent seismograph, 2) f-mode oscillation frequencies are surprisingly insensitive to most uncertainties, but 3) are sensitive to planetary core size and differential rotation, 4) several C-ring features may be self-consistently associated with five low degree f-mode oscillations of Saturn, and 5) the proposed associations are testable by future observations.

Perhaps the most startling result is the planetary oscillation amplitude capable of perturbing the ring system. Oscillation amplitudes (at $r = R$) ranging from 2 to 30 cm are sufficient to launch waves in the C-ring. These amplitudes correspond to mode velocities of $\sim 10^{-3} \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Deming *et al.* (1989) searched for p-modes at Jupiter and placed an upper limit at 1 m s^{-1} for the total velocity amplitude

of detectable modes. They were most sensitive to modes $|m| = l < 54$ implying an upper limit to individual mode velocities of $\sim 1 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$. Presumably the same technique applied to Saturn would produce an even larger upper limit. Ring seismology is thus at least 3 orders of magnitude more sensitive to planetary oscillations than current state of the art telescopic techniques. This comparison is not strictly appropriate, however, since Deming *et al.* were most sensitive to the shorter period p-modes which reflect near the tropopause. The longer period f-modes reflect deeper in the planet (for a discussion of mode reflection in the Jovian case, see Bercovici and Schubert 1987) and may not produce a detectable atmospheric signal. Thus the f-modes may only be detectable in the gravitational field while the shorter period p-modes are only detectable telescopically. In any event, attempts to telescopically detect planetary oscillations have been confined to Jupiter.

The low oscillation amplitude necessary to produce ring features is attributable to several physical traits of the system. First, the C-ring has a relatively small surface mass density. This reduces the force necessary to produce observable features. Second, the f-modes involve oscillations over a large fraction of the volume of the planet. Thus even very low amplitude oscillations perturb a large volume and consequently a large mass. The Prometheus 2:1 ILR in the C-ring, for example, may be associated with a gap/ringlet feature (see Section 3.5) and $M_{\text{Pro}}/M_{\text{Sat}} = 1.2 \times 10^{-9}$. A wave height of about 10 cm on a uniform density Saturn would perturb a similar fraction of the mass of the planet, in good agreement with the more careful calculation in Section 5.4. Third, the phenomenon of resonance amplifies the weak planetary signal. Steady, small amplitude perturbations can produce significant effects in the ring plane. As evidenced by numerous other satellite produced ring features, away from resonance there is no trace of the satellite in the rings. At

resonance, unmistakable gaps and waves are produced. For the long period f-mode oscillations, which produce a significant perturbation to the external gravitation field, there may be no better detector. For the p-modes, which have numerous radial nodes in the radial displacement eigenfunction and thus produce little gravitational perturbation, other detection methods must be used.

Although the forcing of oscillation modes by convection in the planet is not well understood, the mode amplitudes predicted by most models do not fall far below those discussed above. Since the nature of convection in Saturn is also uncertain, such theoretical conclusions are themselves quite approximate. Definite detection of oscillation mode amplitudes could thus help to significantly improve and constrain both theories of mode excitation and perhaps convective velocities in Saturn.

The range of planetary oscillation frequencies calculated in Chapter 4 are also a useful new result. While various approximations of mode frequencies may be made in different limits, there is no substitute for full solution of the set of fourth order differential equations in the case of low degree low radial order oscillation modes, like the f-modes investigated here. The study of various models determined that the principal sources of eigenfrequency uncertainty are, for very low degree modes, interior model variation, and for higher degree modes, the size and magnitude of planetary differential rotation. In any case, eigenfrequencies can be calculated within no more than 1% accuracy.

For each oscillation mode, the significant resonance lying furthest from the planet is the $m : m + 1$ Outer Lindblad Resonance, where the oscillation order m is equal to the degree l (*i.e.*, sectoral modes). Fortunately these resonances fall in the C-ring of Saturn. If the oscillation periods were shorter, no resonances would

lie in the rings. If the periods were longer, the resonances would lie in the optically thick B-ring where there is very little data on waves. Interestingly enough, the resonance locations fall in the region of the C-ring where there are numerous wave features which are not associated with known satellites.

These unassociated features, identified by Rosen (1989), are characterized by low values of azimuthal wavenumber, $m \lesssim 10$. This implies that if these waves are excited by satellites, the satellite cannot be close by. A putative satellite imbedded in the Keeler gap, for example, is believed to be at least partly responsible for a nearby edge distortion with $m \sim 36$ (Cooke *et al.* 1989). But if the C-ring wave producing satellites are far away, their masses must be larger, perhaps so large that they should have been detected. One interpretation of the unassociated C-ring wave at 85690 km, for example, requires a satellite outside of Titan's orbit with approximately the same mass (Rosen 1989). Thus these C-ring waves present especially attractive candidates for planetary excitation since this mechanism naturally produces low m resonances (high m and hence l modes do not probe deeply enough into the planet to perturb a significant fraction of Saturn's mass).

At best, the detailed resonance locations predicted by the planetary oscillation frequency calculation overlap the locations of the Maxwell gap and four of the unassociated C-ring wave features (see Tables 5.3 and 5.4). The other half of the unassociated C-ring waves (Table 5.5) cannot be correlated with oscillation mode resonances. Given the failure to explain all the waves, the theoretical uncertainty of each resonance location (~ 1000 km), and the large resonance position ranges produced by the number of degrees of freedom in the interior models, the proposed associations are not statistically compelling. The additional internal consistencies in the proposed associations, however, provide significant supporting evidence that

these pairings may not be random. All five associations arise from a single Saturn model. The predicted wave types are consistent with the four observed waves (three OLR and one OVR). With one minor exception, the predicted values of m agree with the observed ranges. The proposed progression of effect in the rings from large (gap opening) to intermediate (waves with $\delta\tau/\tau_n \sim 1.4$ (see Table 3.2)) to small (waves with $\delta\tau/\tau_n \sim 0.7$) to no effect, is generally consistent with that predicted by the oscillation excitation and wave production theories. These internal consistencies persuasively argue that the Maxwell gap and the four waves may indeed be produced by planetary oscillation mode resonances.

Fortunately, this hypothesis is testable. The Cassini mission to Saturn should determine unambiguously the wave characteristics of all the unassociated C-ring waves. At that time these characteristics can be compared to those predicted by this hypothesis. It should be stressed, however, that the associations in Tables 5.3 and 5.4 represent only a single, possible set. The data might reveal that a different set of associations is correct. The conclusive signatures to look for in the data will be determination of wave type (density *vs.* bending), range of m (the waves should not all be $m = 3$ for example), and location of resonances with newly discovered satellites. If some subset of the Rosen waves pass all three tests, then they can almost certainly be identified as being produced at planetary acoustic mode resonances.

Regardless of whether or not the Cassini mission confirms the planetary excitation mechanism, the analysis will place significant new constraints on Saturn's interior structure. A null result would set very tight limits on the size of Saturnian f-mode oscillations. A positive result would provide meaningful new information about Saturn's interior structure and deep rotation. If the proposed associations

were correct, for example, one could conclude that the core is slightly larger than standard interior models predict, deep differential rotation is not present, and there may be a slight composition gradient in the interior. Such detailed conclusions, however, await the new millennium and Cassini.

APPENDIX I

ROTATION CORRECTION EQUATIONS

The equations for the rotation corrections to the oscillation eigenfrequencies are presented in this appendix. Since the source equations for the zeroth order eigenmodes (presented in Chapter 2) are adapted from Unno *et al.* (1979) while the rotation corrections are from the Vorontsov papers (Vorontsov 1981; Vorontsov and Zharkov 1981), and since the individual equations are quite complex, I will take the unusual course of using two different sets of notations. The notation used in the preceding chapters is all internally consistent and generally follows Unno *et al.* . This appendix will follow the Vorontsov notation. Since the transformations between the two are straightforward, and since any attempt to revise the detailed equations could lead to numerous errors, I feel this is the best approach. The reader is thus advised to pay careful attention to the commentary and not simply adopt equations as they are presented without careful consideration.

To begin we define the departure of an arbitrary parcel of fluid or gas from its unperturbed position $\mathbf{r}_0$:

$$\vec{\xi}(\mathbf{r}, t) \equiv \mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_0 = \mathbf{u}(\mathbf{r})e^{i\sigma t}. \quad (\text{A1.1})$$

Note that this is the opposite sign convention for the exponential as that used previously. The only consequence is that when the oscillation order m is used in this appendix, it must be the negative of the value used earlier. Now $\mathbf{u}$ can be decomposed into radial and tangential components,

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{l, m, n} = \hat{\mathbf{r}}U(r)Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi) + V(r)\vec{\nabla}_1 Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi), \quad (\text{A1.2})$$

where

$$\vec{\nabla}_1 = \hat{\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} + \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \hat{\varphi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \varphi}. \quad (\text{A1.3})$$

The tilde accent applies to quantities calculated in the absence of rotation. Note that U and V are equivalent to ξ_r and ξ_h from Chapter 2 respectively. To account for rotation we define the small parameter

$$\lambda = \frac{\Omega_0}{\tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n}}, \quad (\text{A1.4})$$

and expand the eigenfunction

$$\mathbf{u}_{l,m,n} = \mathbf{u}_{l,m,n,0} + \lambda \mathbf{u}_{l,m,n,1} + \lambda^2 \mathbf{u}_{l,m,n,2} + \dots \quad (\text{A1.5})$$

and eigenfrequency

$$\sigma_{l,m,n} = \tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n} (1 + \sigma_{l,m,n,1} \lambda + \sigma_{l,m,n,2} \lambda^2 + \dots). \quad (\text{A1.6})$$

The first term in the expansion of the eigenfunction is just the eigenfunction for the case of no rotation

$$\mathbf{u}_{l,m,n,0} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{l,m,n}. \quad (\text{A1.7})$$

Since the details of the eigenfunction are not relevant to ring seismology, I do not present the first and second order corrections to the eigenfunctions. Only the corrections for the eigenfrequencies are presented.

Before considering these correction terms, it is necessary to introduce some notation. First, many of the following expressions contain various angular integrals:

$$A_{kJ'J}^{qM'M} = \int_{\Omega} Y_{kq} Y_{J'M'} Y_{JM}^* d\Omega, \quad (\text{A1.8})$$

$$B_{kJ'J}^{qM'M} = \int_{\Omega} Y_{kq} (\vec{\nabla}_1 Y_{J'M'}) \cdot (\vec{\nabla}_1 Y_{JM})^* d\Omega, \quad (\text{A1.9})$$

and

$$C_{kJ'J}^{qM'M} = \int_{\Omega} Y_{kq}(\vec{\nabla}_1 Y_{J'M'}) \cdot (-\hat{\mathbf{r}} \times \vec{\nabla}_1 Y_{JM})^* d\Omega. \quad (\text{A1.10})$$

Asterisks instruct to take the complex conjugate and here only Ω denotes solid angle. These integrals may be computed from analytic expressions in Luh (1974) and Messiah (1962). Additional conventions for U and V are introduced:

$$U_l = mV, \quad V_l = \frac{m}{l(l+1)}(U + V), \quad (\text{A1.11})$$

$$W_{l-1} = -i \left[\frac{(l+m)(l-m)}{l^2(2l+1)(2l-1)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} [U + (l+1)V], \quad (\text{A1.12})$$

and

$$W_{l+1} = i \left[\frac{(l+m+1)(l-m+1)}{(l+1)^2(2l+1)(2l+3)} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} [U - lV]. \quad (\text{A1.13})$$

Finally recall the expansion for differential rotation from Chapter 2:

$$\Omega_{\text{P}} = \Omega_{\text{P}}(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \Omega_{\text{d}}(r, \theta) = \Omega_0 \sum_i^k \Omega_{\text{di}}(r) Y_{i0}(\theta, \varphi). \quad (\text{A1.14})$$

In practice the degree of expansion k does not exceed 2.

The rotation corrections to the eigenfrequencies are then given by

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{l,m,n,1} = \sum_i^k \int_0^a \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 \Omega_{\text{di}} [A_{ill}^{0mm} U(U_l - mU) \\ + B_{ill}^{0mm} V(V_l - mV) + C_{il,l-1}^{0mm*} V W_{l-1} + C_{il,l+1}^{0mm*} V W_{l+1}] dr \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1.15})$$

and

$$2\sigma_{l,m,n,2} - \sigma_{l,m,n,1}^2 = K_{1t} + K_{1s} + K_2 + K_3 \quad (\text{A1.16})$$

where a and $\tilde{\rho}_0$ are the planetary radius and density distribution in the absence of rotation. These expressions are only valid for normalized eigenfunctions. When

using generalized eigenfunctions, the terms to the right of the equals sign in both (A1.15) and (A1.16) must be divided by

$$\int_0^a \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 [U^2 + l(l+1)V^2] dr. \quad (\text{A1.17})$$

The first and third terms in the second order correction are given by

$$\begin{aligned} K_{1t} = & -4 \int_0^a \sum_{i,j,l'} \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 \Omega_{di} \Omega_{dj} \frac{1}{l'(l'+1)} \\ & \times [C_{il'l}^{0mm} C_{jl'l}^{0mm} (V_l - mV)^2 + B_{il',l-1}^{0mm} B_{jl',l-1}^{0mm} W_{l-1}^2 \\ & + B_{il',l+1}^{0mm} B_{jl',l+1}^{0mm} W_{l+1}^2 + 2C_{il'l}^{0mm} B_{jl',l-1}^{0mm} (V_l - mV) W_{l-1} \\ & + 2C_{il'l}^{0mm} B_{jl',l+1}^{0mm} (V_l - mV) W_{l+1} \\ & + 2B_{il',l-1}^{0mm} B_{jl',l+1}^{0mm} W_{l-1} W_{l+1}] dr \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1.18})$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} K_2 = & m \sum_{i,j,l'} \int_0^a \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 \Omega_{di} \Omega_{dj} \frac{1}{l'(l'+1)} \\ & \times [l'(l'+1) A_{il'l}^{0mm} A_{jl'l}^{0mm} U(2U_l - mU) \\ & + B_{il'l}^{0mm} B_{jl'l}^{0mm} V(2V_l - mV) + 2B_{il'l}^{0mm} C_{jl',l-1}^{0mm*} V W_{l-1} \\ & + 2B_{il'l}^{0mm} C_{jl',l+1}^{0mm*} V W_{l+1} + C_{il'l}^{0mm*} C_{jl'l}^{0mm} V(2V_l - mV) \\ & + 2C_{il'l}^{0mm*} B_{jl',l-1}^{0mm} V W_{l-1} + 2C_{il'l}^{0mm*} B_{jl',l+1}^{0mm} V W_{l+1}] dr \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A1.19})$$

In the above expansions the summation over i and j ranges from 0 to k while $l' = (l - k - 1, l - k, \dots, l + k, l + k + 1)$. Several small typographical errors in Vorontsov (1981) have been corrected here. The second term is

$$K_{1s} = \sum_{l',n'} \frac{\tilde{\omega}_{l',m,n}^2 - \tilde{\omega}_{l',m,n'}^2}{\tilde{\omega}_{l',m,n}^2} (a_{l',m,n,1}^{l',m,n'})^2 \quad (\text{A1.20})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
a_{l,m,n,1}^{l',m,n'} &= \frac{\tilde{\omega}_{l,m,n}^2}{\tilde{\omega}_{l,m,n}^2 - \tilde{\omega}_{l',m,n'}^2} 2 \sum_i^k \int_0^a \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 \Omega_{di} [A_{il'l}^{0mm} U'(U_l - mU) \\
&\quad + B_{il'l}^{0mm} V'(V_l - mV) + C_{il',l-1}^{0mm*} V' W_{l-1} \\
&\quad + C_{il',l+1}^{0mm*} V' W_{l+1}] dr.
\end{aligned} \tag{A1.21}$$

Here $l' = (l - k, l - k + 1, \dots, l + k - 1, l + k)$ and n' ranges from 0 to ∞ . As n' increases, the corrections become smaller and in practice n' need be no greater than about 4 for f-mode corrections. U' and V' are the radial multipliers in the eigenfunction $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{l',m,n'}$ corresponding to $\tilde{\sigma}_{l',m,n'}$.

The final component in the rotation correction is the term K_3 :

$$\Omega^2 K_3 = I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4 + I_5 + I_6. \tag{A1.22}$$

The terms in this expression, which account for centrifugal force and ellipticity of figure, are presented in Vorontsov and Zharkov (1981) where they are derived for the case of solid body rotation. The interior models used for calculating the zero order oscillation frequencies use a figure theory which assumes solid body rotation. Thus to be internally consistent the rotation correction for ellipticity of figure uses the figure determined for solid body rotation. The individual terms are given by

$$I_1 = A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a K_{10} r^2 (\partial_r U + F)^2 dr, \tag{A1.23}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2 &= A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \frac{1}{2} \rho_{10} r^2 [(8\pi G \tilde{\rho}_0 - 4r^{-1} \partial_r \tilde{\psi}_0) U^2 - 2\partial_r \tilde{\psi}_0 U F] dr \\
&\quad + B_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \rho_{10} r^2 [r^{-1} \partial_r \tilde{\psi}_0 UV] dr,
\end{aligned} \tag{A1.24}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_3 = & A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a r^2 \left\{ g_{10} \tilde{\rho}_0 [6r^{-2}U^2 + 6r^{-1}UF] \right. \\
& + \rho_{10} [4\pi G \tilde{\rho}_0 U^2 + 8\pi Gr^{-3} \int_0^r \tilde{\rho}_0 (r')^3 UF dr'] \left. \right\} dr \\
& + B_{i2l}^{-m0-m} \int_0^a r^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} g_{10} \tilde{\rho}_0 [r^{-1}U \partial_r V - r^{-1}V(\partial_r U + F)] \right. \\
& + (l(l+1)V - 4U)r^{-2}V \\
& - \rho_{10} [2\pi Gr^{-3} \int_0^r \tilde{\rho}_0 (r')^2 UV dr'] \left. \right\} dr \\
& + B_{i2l}^{m0m} \int_0^a r^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{2} g_{10} \tilde{\rho}_0 [r^{-1}U \partial_r V - r^{-1}V(\partial_r U + F)] \right. \\
& + (l(l+1)V - 4U)r^{-2}V \\
& - \rho_{10} [2\pi Gr^{-3} \int_0^r \tilde{\rho}_0 (r')^2 UV dr'] \left. \right\} dr,
\end{aligned} \tag{A1.25}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_4 = & \frac{2}{3} (4\pi)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Omega^2 \left\{ A_{0il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 [U^2 - 2l(l+1)UV] dr \right. \\
& + A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \frac{1}{\sqrt{5}} \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 [2l(l+1)UV - U^2] dr \\
& + B_{i2l}^{-m0-m} \int_0^a \frac{1}{4\sqrt{5}} \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 [rU \partial_r V - rV \partial_r U - UV \\
& \quad + 2l(l+1)V^2] dr \\
& + B_{i2l}^{m0m} \int_0^a \frac{1}{4\sqrt{5}} \tilde{\rho}_0 r^2 [rU \partial_r V - rV \partial_r U - UV \\
& \quad + 2l(l+1)V^2] dr \left. \right\},
\end{aligned} \tag{A1.26}$$

$$I_5 = -A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a 2\rho_{10} r^2 U \partial_r P dr - B_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \rho_{10} r VP dr, \tag{A1.27}$$

and

$$I_6 = -(\tilde{\sigma}_{l,m,n})^2 \left[A_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \rho_{10} r^2 U^2 dr + B_{2il}^{0mm} \int_0^a \rho_{10} r^2 V^2 dr \right]. \tag{A1.28}$$

Here $\partial_r \equiv \partial/\partial r$,

$$F(r) = r^{-1} [2U(r) - l(l+1)V(r)], \tag{A1.29}$$

and

$$P(r) = \frac{-\psi_1}{Y_{lm}(\theta, \varphi)}. \quad (\text{A1.30})$$

$\tilde{\psi}_0$ is the gravitational potential of the non-rotating planet, ψ_1 is the perturbation to the potential produced by the oscillation. The terms with subscript ‘10’ account for the deformation of the material parameters of the planet by rotation and are defined:

$$\rho_{10}(r)Y_{20}(\theta, \varphi) \equiv \left[\frac{2}{3}\epsilon(r)r\partial_r\tilde{\rho}_0(r) \right] P_2^0(\cos\theta), \quad (\text{A1.31})$$

$$K_{10}(r)Y_{20}(\theta, \varphi) \equiv \left[\frac{2}{3}\epsilon(r)r\partial_r\tilde{K}(r) \right] P_2^0(\cos\theta), \quad (\text{A1.32})$$

and

$$g_{10}(r) = -\frac{4}{5}\pi G \left[\frac{1}{r^3} \int_0^r \rho_{10}(r)r^4 dr + r^2 \int_r^a \rho_{10}(r)r^{-1} dr \right]. \quad (\text{A1.33})$$

The ellipticity of level surfaces, $\epsilon(r)$, is provided by the planetary interior models. All derivatives of material parameters, the gravitational potential, and the planetary radius should be that applicable to a non-rotating planet with a radius equal to the mean radius of the rotating planet. The term K_3 then accounts for rotation through first order in figure theory.

Vorontsov and Zharkov (1981) present further terms in K_3 which account for discrete jumps in the material parameters of the planet, such as would occur at a distinct core or molecular to metallic hydrogen phase transition. For reasons discussed in Section 2.2, discrete interfaces are not used in the models and these corrections are not reproduced here.

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